

List of Brazilian Amphibians

Magno V. Segalla^{1*}, Bianca Berneck², Clarissa Canedo^{3,4}, Ulisses Caramaschi⁴, Carlos Alberto Gonçalves Cruz⁴, Paulo C. A. Garcia⁵, Taran Grant⁶, Célio F. B. Haddad², Ana Carolina C. Lourenço⁷, Sarah Mângia⁸, Tamí Mott⁹, Luciana B. Nascimento¹⁰, Luís Felipe Toledo¹¹, Fernanda P. Werneck¹², José A. Langone¹³

1 Laboratório de Herpetologia, Museu de História Natural Capão da Imbuia, 82810-080 Curitiba, PR, Brasil.

2 Departamento de Biodiversidade e Centro de Aquicultura, Instituto de Biociências, Universidade Estadual Paulista, Caixa Postal 199, 13506-906 Rio Claro, SP, Brasil.

3 Departamento de Zoologia, Instituto de Biologia Roberto Alcântara Gomes, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro, Rua São Francisco Xavier 524, 20550-900 Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brasil.

4 Departamento de Vertebrados, Museu Nacional, Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, Quinta da Boa Vista, São Cristóvão, 20940-040 Rio de Janeiro, RJ, Brasil.

5 Departamento de Zoologia, Instituto de Ciências Biológicas; Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Avenida Antônio Carlos 6627, 31270-901 Belo Horizonte, MG, Brasil.

6 Departamento de Zoologia, Instituto de Biociências, Universidade de São Paulo, 05508-090 São Paulo, SP, Brasil

7 Departamento de Ciências Biológicas, Universidade do Estado de Minas Gerais, Campus Ubá, Avenida Olegário Maciel 1427, 36502-000 Ubá, MG, Brasil

8 Laboratório de Zoologia, Instituto de Biociências. Universidade Federal de Mato Grosso do Sul, 79070-900 Campo Grande, MS, Brasil.

9 Instituto de Ciências Biológicas e da Saúde, Universidade Federal de Alagoas, Av Lourival Melo Mota, 57072-900 Maceió, AL, Brasil

10 Programa de Pós-Graduação em Biologia de Vertebrados, Museu de Ciências Naturais, Pontifícia Universidade Católica de Minas Gerais, 30535-610 Belo Horizonte, MG, Brasil.

11 Laboratório de História Natural de Anfíbios Brasileiros, Departamento de Biologia Animal, Instituto de Biologia, UNICAMP, 13083-862 Campinas, SP, Brasil.

12 Programa de Coleções Científicas Biológicas, Coordenação de Biodiversidade, Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas da Amazônia, 69067-375 Manaus, AM, Brasil.

13 Departamento de Herpetología, Museo Nacional de Historia Natural, Casilla de Correo 399, 11000 Montevideo, Uruguay.

* Corresponding author: msegalla@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4716176](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4716176)

The following list (Tab. 1) includes all recognized species of amphibians, known by vouchers or published information to occur within the political borders of Brazil (as of April 2021). Supra-generic taxonomy follows Frost (2021), as do most generic and species names. Other taxonomic decisions and species exclusions are explained below. All inclusions relative to the previous list (Segalla et al. 2019) are informed in the status column. The known amphibian fauna of Brazil comprises 1188 species, an increase of 95 species compared to the previous list. The vast majority of species are anurans, including 1144 species (two exotic and invasive species) representing 20 families and 107 genera, followed by caecilians, with 39 species in 4 families and 13 genera, and salamanders, with 5 species in a single family and genus.

Registration in Zoobank: urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:D19AF1F3-AEF4-40BD-91E-6-43AA8313E2D2

Species removed from the previous list (Segalla et al. 2019):

Hypsiboas bandeirantes, *Hypsiboas beckeri* and *Hypsiboas latistriata*, synonyms of *Boana polytaenia* (Faivovich et al. 2021);

Hypsiboas phaeopleura, a synonym of *Boana goiana* (Faivovich et al. 2021);

Leptodactylus chaquensis, a synonym of *Leptodactylus macrosternum* (Magalhães et al. 2020a);

Oreobates crepitans, a synonym of *Oreobates heterodactylus* (Pansonato et al. 2020);

Pristimantis achuar, a synonym of *Pristimantis luscombei* (Ortega-Andrade & Venegas 2014);

Proceratophrys aridus and *Proceratophrys caramaschii*, synonyms of *Proceratophrys cristiceps* (Mângia et al. 2020a);

Rhinella abei, a synonym of *R. ornata*;

Rhinella fernandezae, a synonym of *R. dorbignyi*;

Rhinella gildae, a synonym of *R. dapsilis*;

Rhinella jimi, a synonym of *Rhinella diptycha*;

Rhinella martyi, a synonym of *R. margaritifera*;

Rhinella paraguayensis, a synonym of *Rhinella scitula* (Pereyra et al. 2021);

Sphaenorhynchus orophilus, a synonym of *Sphaenorhynchus platycephalus* (Araujo-Vieira et al. 2018);

Crossodactylus aeneus, a synonym of *Crossodactylus gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841 (Vittorazi et al. 2021);

Pseudopaludicola parnaiba, a synonym of *Pseudopaludicola canga* (Andrade et al. 2020b);

Caecilia mertensi was replaced by *C. marculsi* (Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011).

Taxonomic remarks related to Dubois et al. (2021) publication:

Aquarana Dubois, 1992

Dubois et al. (2021) proposed the elevation of the former subgenus *Aquarana* to the new status of genus for the previous *Lithobates catesbeianus* species group, which includes *A. catesbeiana* (Shaw, 1802), the only species of the group that occurs in Brazil. The group is monophyletic and therefore we consider the proposal could be followed and here is considered valid.

Alainia Duellman & Cannatella, 2018 and ***Eothea*** Duellman, 2015

Dubois et al. (2021) erected *Alainia* (proposed as a new name for *Australothea* Duellman, 2015, subgenus of *Gastrothea*) for the following species: *G. albolineata*, *G. ernestoi*, *G. fulvorufa*, and *G. microdiscus*. Likewise, erected *Eothea* (subgenus of *Gastrothea*) for the following species: *Gastrothea fissipes*, *G. prasina*, *G. pulchra*, *G. recava*, and by implication, *G. flamma* and *G. megacephala*. The proposal agrees with recent studies (Duellman 2015; Castroviejo-Fisher et al. 2015) that consider these groups as subgenera (Duellman 2015) or group of species (Castroviejo-Fischer et al. 2015). Both genera are diagnosed and supported by molecular and morphological data (Duellman 2015; Castroviejo-Fisher et al. 2015). Therefore, although we considered it a notarial change not resolving taxonomic problems, we accepted the proposal.

Cycloramphus Tschudi, 1838

Dubois et al. (2021) synonymized *Zachaenus* Cope, 1866 with *Cycloramphus*, as *Cycloramphus* was paraphyletic with respect to *Zachaenus* in their tree—a finding first reported by Sabbag et al. (2018) and de Sá et al. (2020). We agree with this act; however, Dubois et al. (2021) failed to observe that, in proposing the synonymy, two valid species names are now secondary homonyms: *Cycloramphus carvalhoi* Heyer, 1983 and *Cycloramphus carvalhoi* (Izecksohn, 1983 “1982”). Heyer’s article became available in October, 1983. According to the information printed in the journal, the January/June 1982 issue (Volume 5, Number 1) of *Arquivos da Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro*, which contains Izecksohn’s article, was issued 16 December 1982; however, it has long been understood that the issue became available in 1983, and the copy at the Museu de Zoologia da USP was received on 27 April 1983. In either case, Izecksohn’s name has priority as the senior homonym, and the species described by Heyer requires a nomen novum. Therefore, we propose the replacement name *Cycloramphus heyeri* nom. nov. in honor of W. Ronald Heyer, the author of the original species description (see Heyer, 1983).

Engystoma Fitzinger, 1826

Dubois et al. (2021) resurrected the genus *Engystoma* to include all species currently included in the genus *Elachistocleis* Parker, 1927 on the basis of the assumption that *Rana ovalis* Schneider, 1799 is the type species of both genera and, by date, the first name has priority over the second. Fitzinger (1826:39) diagnosed the genus *Engystoma* by its narrow mouth, tetradactyl hands and pentactyl feet (“*Rictus angustus, palmae tetradactylidae, plantae*”). On the next page (Fitzinger, 1826:40) he clearly indicates that the representative (“*Repräsentant*”) for this genus is *Rana gibbosa* Linnaeus, 1758 and refers to the inclusion of this species in the genus *Breviceps* by Merrem (1820). Fitzinger did not agree with the characters that Merrem used to diagnose *Breviceps*, arguing that they can also be extended to species from other genera, and commented that *Rana bufonia*, *Bufo ventricosus*, *Bombinator ventricosus*, [*Bombinator*] *Systema*, and *Pipa laevis* are “true Engystomas” (*wahre Engystomen* in the original). On this page there is no mention of *Rana ovalis*. Later, the author (Fitzinger 1826:65) included in combination with the genus *Engystoma*: *Rana ovalis* Schneider, 1799; *Rana gibbosa* Linnaeus, 1758 and *Rana ventricosa* Linnaeus, 1758, in this order, and did not mention the other “true Engystomas”.

Based on this review we concluded that:

- a) With the word “*Repräsentant*” Fitzinger clearly designates *Rana gibbosa* as the type species of the genus *Engystoma* [In the same paragraph and in the same way that he designates *Bufo ephippium* as “*Represäntant*” of *Brachycephalus*, a designation not disputed by Dubois et al. (2021)].
- b) This invalidates the subsequent designation by Duméril & Bibron (1841) of *Rana ovalis* as the type species of *Engystoma*.
- c) *Engystoma* is a junior synonym of *Breviceps* Merrem, 1820.

Eupemphix Steidachner, 1863

Dubois et al. (2021) proposed the resurrection of *Eupemphix* for the *Physalaemus signifer* clade of Lourenço et al. (2015), indicating that, based on their method, they did not find support for the genus *Physalaemus* Fitzinger, 1826, including two groups: *Physalaemus cuvieri* clade and *Physalaemus signifer* clade. However, they used only part of the species of each clade and disregarded the higher density of taxa as proposed by Lourenço et al. (2015) and Leal et al. (2020), who recovered *Physalaemus* with high support. Thus, we consider that the proposal by Dubois et al. (2021) should not be followed and maintain *Physalaemus* for both clades. In this case *Eupemphix* persists as a junior synonym of *Physalaemus*.

Hylodes Fitzinger, 1826

Dubois et al. (2021) considered the genus *Megaelosia* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923 to be a synonym of *Hylodes*. However, considering the recovered relationship, both genera could be recognized with a simple rearrangement of species. As few species of *Hylodes* and only one of *Megaelosia* were included in Dubois et al. (2021), and both genera are supported by morphological data, we prefer to maintain both genera until a more comprehensive analysis is available.

Pseudis Wagler, 1830

Dubois et al. (2021) placed the genus *Lysapsus* Cope, 1862 as a junior synonym of *Pseudis*. However, here we do not follow this taxonomic proposal, as the authors agreed that there is no need for such synonymization and recognition of both genera has been widely accepted.

Relictocleis Dubois, Ohler & Pyron 2021

Dubois et al. (2021) designated *Relictocleis* as a subgenus of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904. This is a new name for *Relictus* (from de Sá et al. 2019a) and *Unicus* (from de Sá et al. 2019b; from de Sá et al. 2019c), which are invalid names according to the Code (Articles 13.1.3 and 16.1). *Relictocleis*, with *Chiasmocleis gnoma* Canedo, Dixo & Pombal, 2004 as type species, is diagnosed and supported by molecular and morphological data (de Sá et al. 2019c; Dubois et al. 2021). Because *Relictocleis* has a basal position in the phylogeny, occurs in isolation from the ranges of other *Chiasmocleis*, and according the analysis of de Sá et al. (2019a) diverged early in the history of the group, probably during the late Eocene-Oligocene (33-35 mya), we consider this lineage to represent a monophyletic genus in the combination *Relictocleis gnoma* (Canedo, Dixo e Pombal, 2004).

Scinax Wagler, 1830

In a reanalysis of hylid sequences on GenBank, Duellman et al. (2016) suggested splitting *Scinax* into three genera: *Julianus* Duellman, Marion & Hedges, 2016 for the *Scinax uruguayus* species group (Faivovich et al. 2005), *Ololygon* Fitzinger, 1843 for the *Scinax catharinae* clade (*sensu* Faivovich 2002 and Faivovich et al. 2005), and *Scinax* for all remaining species of the *S. ruber* clade (*sensu* Faivovich et al. 2005). However, Lourenço et al. (2016) did not follow the resurrection of *Ololygon* or the erection of *Julianus*, concluding that these changes are strictly optional in that they are not required to preserve the monophyly of the existing taxonomic arrangement, which by itself has been repeatedly corroborated since Faivovich et al. (2005). They also pointed out that, instead, the suggested changes proposed by Duellman et al. (2016) derive from poorly discussed and inconsistently applied criteria that resulted in definitions without any regard for synapomorphies, either those proposed by earlier authors or by themselves (the term synapomorphy does not appear in any part of the document, for example). Similarly, Colaço & Silva (2016) also refused to partition *Scinax* into three genera, considering that Duellman et al. (2016) ignored most of the morphological characters known and common to all species of the genus (addressed mainly by Faivovich 2002). Although the rejection of the Duellman et al. (2016) proposal is not universal in the literature (e.g., Santos-Pereira et al. 2018; Ferreira et al. 2019; Forti et al. 2019; Segalla et al. 2019; Zornosa-Torres et al. 2020), it has been followed in some subsequent articles (e.g., Faivovich et al. 2018; Baldo et al. 2019; Lourenço et al. 2019; Lourenço et al. 2020; Araújo-Vieira 2020; Novaes-e-Fagundes et al. 2021; Dubois et al. 2021). Here, we

follow the arguments of Lourenço et al. (2016) and Colaço & Silva (2016) that indicate that *Julianus* and *Ololygon* should be considered junior synonyms of *Scinax*, until the morphological evidence already available for the group is considered.

Stombus Gravenhorst, 1825

Dubois et al. (2021) recognized *Ceratophrys calcarata* Boulenger, 1890 and *C. cornuta* (Linnaeus 1758) as belonging to the genus *Stombus*. However, if *Stombus* is revalidated as proposed, *Ceratophrys* Wied-Neuwied, 1824 would be paraphyletic. Thus, we do not follow the proposal of Dubois et al. (2021) and instead maintain the use of the genus *Ceratophrys* for *C. cornuta* and *C. calcarata*, with *Stombus* still considered a junior synonym of *Ceratophrys* (Frost 2021).

Table 1. List of amphibians of Brazil

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
Family Allophrynidae	1 gen, 3 spp
1. <i>Allophryne relictata</i> Caramaschi, Orrico, Faivovich, Dias & Solé, 2013	
2. <i>Allophryne resplendens</i> Castroviejo-Fisher, Pérez-Peña, Padial & Guayasamin, 2012	
3. <i>Allophryne ruthveni</i> Gaige, 1926	
Family Alsodidae	1 gen, 1 sp
4. <i>Limnomedusa macroglossa</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	
Family Aromobatidae (Allobatinae)	1 gen, 31 spp
5. <i>Allobates bacurau</i> Simões, 2016	
6. <i>Allobates brunneus</i> (Cope, 1887)	
7. <i>Allobates caeruleodactylus</i> (Lima & Caldwell, 2001)	
8. <i>Allobates caldwella</i> Lima, Ferrão & Silva, 2020	recently described species
9. <i>Allobates carajas</i> Simões, Rojas & Lima, 2019	
10. <i>Allobates conspicuus</i> (Morales, 2002)	
11. <i>Allobates crombiei</i> (Morales, 2002)	
12. <i>Allobates femoralis</i> (Boulenger, 1884)	
13. <i>Allobates flaviventris</i> Melo-Sampaio, Souza & Peloso, 2013	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
14. <i>Allobates fuscillus</i> (Morales, 2002)	
15. <i>Allobates gasconi</i> (Morales, 2002)	
16. <i>Allobates goianus</i> (Bokermann, 1975)	
17. <i>Allobates grillisimilis</i> Simões, Sturaro, Peloso & Lima, 2013	
18. <i>Allobates hodli</i> Simões, Lima & Farias, 2010	
19. <i>Allobates juami</i> Simões, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Rojas-Runjaic & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2018	
20. <i>Allobates magnussoni</i> Lima, Simões & Kaefer, 2014	
21. <i>Allobates marchesianus</i> (Melin, 1941)	
22. <i>Allobates masniger</i> (Morales, 2002)	
23. <i>Allobates myersi</i> (Pyburn, 1981)	
24. <i>Allobates nidicola</i> (Caldwell & Lima, 2003)	
25. <i>Allobates nunciatus</i> Moraes, Pavan & Lima, 2019	recently described species
26. <i>Allobates olfersioides</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
27. <i>Allobates pacaas</i> Melo-Sampaio, Prates, Peloso, Recoder, Dal Vechio, Marques-Souza & Rodrigues, 2020	recently described species
28. <i>Allobates paleovarzensis</i> Lima, Caldwell, Biavati & Montanarin, 2010	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
29. <i>Allobates subfolionidificans</i> (Lima, Sanchez & Souza, 2007)	
30. <i>Allobates sumtuosus</i> (Morales, 2002)	
31. <i>Allobates tapajos</i> Lima, Simões & Kaefer, 2015	
32. <i>Allobates tinae</i> Melo-Sampaio, Oliveira & Prates, 2018	
33. <i>Allobates trilineatus</i> (Boulenger, 1884)	
34. <i>Allobates vanzolinius</i> (Morales, 2002)	
35. <i>Allobates velocicantus</i> Souza, Ferrão, Hanken & Lima, 2020	recently described species
Family Aromobatidae (Anomaloglossinae)	1 gen, 5 spp
36. <i>Anomaloglossus apiau</i> Fouquet, Souza, Nunes, Kok, Curcio, Carvalho, Grant & Rodrigues, 2015	
37. <i>Anomaloglossus baeobatrachus</i> (Boistel & de Massari, 1999)	
38. <i>Anomaloglossus stepheni</i> (Martins, 1989)	
39. <i>Anomaloglossus tamacuarensis</i> (Myers & Donnelly, 1997)	
40. <i>Anomaloglossus tepequem</i> Fouquet, Souza, Nunes, Kok, Curcio, Carvalho, Grant & Rodrigues, 2015	
Family Brachycephalidae	2 gen, 71 spp
41. <i>Brachycephalus actaeus</i> Monteiro, Condez, Garcia, Comitti, Amaral & Haddad, 2018	
42. <i>Brachycephalus albolineatus</i> Bornschein, Ribeiro, Blackburn, Stanley & Pie, 2016	

ORDER ANURA

STATUS

43. *Brachycephalus alipioi* Pombal & Gasparini, 2006
44. *Brachycephalus atelopoide* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
45. *Brachycephalus auroguttatus* Ribeiro, Firkowski, Bornschein & Pie, 2015
46. *Brachycephalus boticario* Pie, Bornschein, Firkowski, Belmonte-Lopes & Ribeiro, 2015
47. *Brachycephalus brunneus* Ribeiro, Alves, Haddad & Reis, 2005
48. *Brachycephalus bufonoides* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
49. *Brachycephalus coloratus* Ribeiro, Blackburn, Stanley, Pie & Bornschein, 2017
50. *Brachycephalus crispus* Condez, Clemente-Carvalho & Haddad, 2014
51. *Brachycephalus curupira* Ribeiro, Blackburn, Stanley, Pie & Bornschein, 2017
52. *Brachycephalus darkside* Guimarães, Luz, Rocha & Feio, 2017
53. *Brachycephalus didactylus* (Izecksohn, 1971)
54. *Brachycephalus ephippium* (Spix, 1824)
55. *Brachycephalus ferruginus* Alves, Ribeiro, Haddad & Reis, 2006
56. *Brachycephalus fuscolineatus* Pie, Bornschein, Firkowski, Belmonte-Lopes & Ribeiro, 2015
57. *Brachycephalus garbeanus* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920
58. *Brachycephalus guarani* Clemente-Carvalho, Giaretta, Condez, Haddad & Reis, 2012

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
59. <i>Brachycephalus hermogenesi</i> (Giaretta & Sawaya, 1998)	
60. <i>Brachycephalus izecksohni</i> Ribeiro, Alves, Haddad & Reis, 2005	
61. <i>Brachycephalus leopardus</i> Ribeiro, Firkowski & Pie, 2015	
62. <i>Brachycephalus margaritatus</i> Pombal & Izecksohn, 2011	
63. <i>Brachycephalus mariaterezae</i> Bornschein, Morato, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Pie, 2015	new spelling
64. <i>Brachycephalus mirissimus</i> Pie, Ribeiro, Confetti, Nadaline & Bornschein, 2018	
65. <i>Brachycephalus nodoterga</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920	
66. <i>Brachycephalus olivaceus</i> Bornschein, Morato, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Pie, 2015	
67. <i>Brachycephalus pernix</i> Pombal, Wistuba & Bornschein, 1998	
68. <i>Brachycephalus pitanga</i> Alves, Sawaya, Reis & Haddad, 2009	
69. <i>Brachycephalus pombali</i> Alves, Ribeiro, Haddad & Reis, 2006	
70. <i>Brachycephalus pulex</i> Napoli, Caramaschi, Cruz & Dias, 2011	
71. <i>Brachycephalus quiririensis</i> Pie & Ribeiro, 2015	
72. <i>Brachycephalus sulfuratus</i> Condez, Monteiro, Comitti, Garcia, Amaral & Haddad, 2016	
73. <i>Brachycephalus toby</i> Haddad, Alves, Clemente-Carvalho & Reis, 2010	
74. <i>Brachycephalus tridactylus</i> Garey, Lima, Hartmann & Haddad, 2012	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
75. <i>Brachycephalus verrucosus</i> Ribeiro, Firkowski, Bornschein & Pie, 2015	
76. <i>Brachycephalus vertebralis</i> Pombal, 2001	
77. <i>Ischnocnema abdita</i> Canedo & Pimenta, 2010	
78. <i>Ischnocnema bocaina</i> Taucce, Zaidan, Zaher & Garcia, 2019	recently described species
79. <i>Ischnocnema bolbodactyla</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
80. <i>Ischnocnema colibri</i> Taucce, Canedo, Parreiras, Drummond, Nogueira-Costa & Haddad, 2018	
81. <i>Ischnocnema concolor</i> Targino, Costa & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2009	
82. <i>Ischnocnema epipeda</i> (Heyer, 1984)	
83. <i>Ischnocnema erythromera</i> (Heyer, 1984)	
84. <i>Ischnocnema feioi</i> Taucce, Canedo & Haddad, 2018	
85. <i>Ischnocnema garciai</i> Taucce, Canedo & Haddad, 2018	
86. <i>Ischnocnema gehrti</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
87. <i>Ischnocnema gualteri</i> (B. Lutz, 1974)	
88. <i>Ischnocnema guentheri</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
89. <i>Ischnocnema henselii</i> (Peters, 1872)	
90. <i>Ischnocnema hoehnei</i> (B. Lutz, 1958)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
91. <i>Ischnocnema holti</i> (Cochran, 1948)	
92. <i>Ischnocnema izecksohni</i> (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989)	
93. <i>Ischnocnema juipoca</i> (Sazima & Cardoso, 1978)	
94. <i>Ischnocnema karst</i> Canedo, Targino, Leite & Haddad, 2012	
95. <i>Ischnocnema lactea</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923)	
96. <i>Ischnocnema manezinho</i> (Garcia, 1996)	
97. <i>Ischnocnema melanopygia</i> Targino, Costa & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2009	
98. <i>Ischnocnema nanahallux</i> Brusquetti, Thomé, Canedo, Condez & Haddad, 2013	
99. <i>Ischnocnema nasuta</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
100. <i>Ischnocnema nigriventris</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
101. <i>Ischnocnema octavioi</i> (Bokermann, 1965)	
102. <i>Ischnocnema oea</i> (Heyer, 1984)	
103. <i>Ischnocnema paranaensis</i> (Langone & Segalla, 1996)	
104. <i>Ischnocnema parnaso</i> Taucce, Canedo, Parreiras, Drummond, Nogueira-Costa & Haddad, 2018	
105. <i>Ischnocnema parva</i> (Girard, 1853)	
106. <i>Ischnocnema penaxavantinho</i> Giaretta, Toffoli & Oliveira, 2007	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
107. <i>Ischnocnema pusilla</i> (Bokermann, 1967)	
108. <i>Ischnocnema randorum</i> (Heyer, 1985)	
109. <i>Ischnocnema sambaqui</i> (Castanho & Haddad, 2000)	
110. <i>Ischnocnema spanios</i> (Heyer, 1985)	
111. <i>Ischnocnema surda</i> Canedo, Pimenta, Leite & Caramaschi, 2010	
112. <i>Ischnocnema venancioi</i> (B. Lutz, 1958)	
113. <i>Ischnocnema verrucosa</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
114. <i>Ischnocnema vizottoi</i> Martins & Haddad, 2010	
Family Bufonidae	8 gen, 100 spp
115. <i>Amazophrynella bilinguis</i> Kaefer, Rojas-Zamora, Ferrão, Farias & Lima, 2019	recently described species
116. <i>Amazophrynella bokermanni</i> (Izecksohn, 1994)	
117. <i>Amazophrynella gardai</i> Mângia, Koroiva & Santana, 2020	recently described species
118. <i>Amazophrynella manaos</i> Rojas, Carvalho, Gordo, Ávila, Farias & Hrbek, 2014	
119. <i>Amazophrynella minuta</i> (Melin, 1941)	
120. <i>Amazophrynella moisesii</i> Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2018	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
121. <i>Amazophrynella teko</i> Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2018	
122. <i>Amazophrynella vote</i> Avila, Carvalho, Gordo, Kawashita-Ribeiro & Morais, 2012	
123. <i>Amazophrynella xinguensis</i> Rojas-Zamora, Fouquet, Ron, Hernández-Ruz, Melo-Sampaio, Chaparro, Vogt, Carvalho, Pinheiro, Ávila, Farias, Gordo & Hrbek, 2018	
124. <i>Atelopus flavescens</i> Duméril & Bibron, 1841	
125. <i>Atelopus franciscanus</i> Lescure, 1974	
126. <i>Atelopus hoogmoedi</i> Lescure, 1974	
127. <i>Atelopus manauensis</i> Jorge, Ferrão & Lima, 2020	recently described species
128. <i>Dendrophryniscus berthaltzae</i> Izecksohn, 1994	
129. <i>Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus</i> Jiménez de la Espada, 1870	
130. <i>Dendrophryniscus carvalhoi</i> Izecksohn, 1994	
131. <i>Dendrophryniscus davori</i> Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato & Brasileiro, 2019	recently described species
132. <i>Dendrophryniscus haddadi</i> Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato & Brasileiro, 2019	recently described species
133. <i>Dendrophryniscus imitator</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	recently revalidated species (Cruz et al., 2019)
134. <i>Dendrophryniscus izecksohni</i> Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato & Brasileiro, 2019	recently described species

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
135. <i>Dendrophryniscus jureia</i> Cruz, Caramaschi, Fusinato & Brasileiro, 2019	recently described species
136. <i>Dendrophryniscus krausae</i> Cruz & Fusinato, 2008	
137. <i>Dendrophryniscus lauroi</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	recently revalidated species (Cruz et al., 2019)
138. <i>Dendrophryniscus leucomystax</i> Izecksohn, 1968	
139. <i>Dendrophryniscus oreites</i> Recoder, Teixeira, Cassimiro, Camacho & Rodrigues, 2010	
140. <i>Dendrophryniscus organensis</i> A. Carvalho-e-Silva, Mongin, Izecksohn & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2010	
141. <i>Dendrophryniscus proboscideus</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	
142. <i>Dendrophryniscus skuki</i> (Caramaschi, 2012)	
143. <i>Dendrophryniscus stawiarskyi</i> Izecksohn, 1994	
144. <i>Frostius erythrophthalmus</i> Pimenta & Caramaschi, 2007	
145. <i>Frostius pernambucensis</i> (Bokermann, 1962)	
146. <i>Melanophryniscus admirabilis</i> Di Bernardo, Maneyro & Grillo, 2006	
147. <i>Melanophryniscus alipioi</i> Langone, Segalla, Bornschein & de Sá, 2008	
148. <i>Melanophryniscus atroluteus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
149. <i>Melanophryniscus biancae</i> Bornschein, Baldo, Pie, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Corrêa, 2015	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
150. <i>Melanophryniscus cambaraensis</i> Braun & Braun, 1979	
151. <i>Melanophryniscus devincenzii</i> Klappenbach, 1968	
152. <i>Melanophryniscus dorsalis</i> (Mertens, 1933)	
153. <i>Melanophryniscus fulvoguttatus</i> (Mertens, 1937)	
154. <i>Melanophryniscus klappenbachi</i> Prigioni & Langone, 2000	
155. <i>Melanophryniscus macrogranulosus</i> Braun, 1973	
156. <i>Melanophryniscus milanoi</i> Baldo, Bornschein, Pie, Firkowski, Ribeiro & Belmonte-Lopes, 2015	
157. <i>Melanophryniscus montevidensis</i> (Philippi, 1902)	
158. <i>Melanophryniscus moreirae</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
159. <i>Melanophryniscus pachyrhynchus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
160. <i>Melanophryniscus peritus</i> Caramaschi & Cruz, 2011	
161. <i>Melanophryniscus sanmartini</i> Klappenbach, 1968	
162. <i>Melanophryniscus setiba</i> Peloso, Faivovich, Grant, Gasparini & Haddad, 2012	
163. <i>Melanophryniscus simplex</i> Caramaschi & Cruz, 2002	
164. <i>Melanophryniscus spectabilis</i> Caramaschi & Cruz, 2002	
165. <i>Melanophryniscus tumifrons</i> (Boulenger, 1905)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
166. <i>Melanophryniscus vilavelhensis</i> Steinback-Padilha, 2009	
167. <i>Melanophryniscus xanthostomus</i> Baldo, Bornschein, Pie, Ribeiro, Firkowski & Morato, 2015	
168. <i>Oreophrynella quelchii</i> (Boulenger, 1895)	
169. <i>Oreophrynella weassipuensis</i> Señaris, DoNascimento & Villarreal, 2005	
170. <i>Rhaebo ceratophrys</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	
171. <i>Rhaebo ecuadorensis</i> Mueses-Cisneros, Cisneros-Heredia & McDiarmid, 2012	
172. <i>Rhaebo guttatus</i> (Schneider, 1799)	
173. <i>Rhinella achavali</i> (Maneyro, Arrieta & de Sá, 2004)	
174. <i>Rhinella acutirostris</i> (Spix, 1824)	
175. <i>Rhinella arenarum</i> (Hensel, 1867)	
176. <i>Rhinella azarai</i> (Gallardo, 1965)	
177. <i>Rhinella bergi</i> (Céspedes, 2000)	
178. <i>Rhinella casconi</i> Roberto, Brito & Thome, 2014	
179. <i>Rhinella castaneotica</i> (Caldwell, 1991)	
180. <i>Rhinella cerradensis</i> Maciel, Brandão, Campos & Sebben, 2007	
181. <i>Rhinella crucifer</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1821)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
182. <i>Rhinella dapsilis</i> (Myers & Carvalho, 1945)	
183. <i>Rhinella diptycha</i> (Cope, 1862)	
184. <i>Rhinella dorbignyi</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	
185. <i>Rhinella exostosica</i> Ferrão, Lima, Ron, Santos & Hanken, 2020	recently described species
186. <i>Rhinella granulosa</i> (Spix, 1824)	
187. <i>Rhinella henseli</i> (A. Lutz, 1934)	
188. <i>Rhinella hoogmoedi</i> Caramaschi & Pombal, 2006	
189. <i>Rhinella icterica</i> (Spix, 1824)	
190. <i>Rhinella inopina</i> Vaz-Silva, Valdujo & Pombal, 2012	
191. <i>Rhinella jimi</i> (Stevaux, 2002)	
192. <i>Rhinella lescurei</i> Fouquet, Gaucher, Blanc & Velez-Rodriguez, 2007	new occurrence (Costa-Campos et al., 2020a)
193. <i>Rhinella magnussoni</i> Lima, Menin & Araújo, 2007	
194. <i>Rhinella major</i> (Müller & Helmich, 1936)	
195. <i>Rhinella margaritifera</i> (Laurenti, 1768)	
196. <i>Rhinella marina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
197. <i>Rhinella merianae</i> (Gallardo, 1965)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
198. <i>Rhinella mirandaribeiroi</i> (Gallardo, 1965)	
199. <i>Rhinella nattereri</i> (Bokermann, 1967)	
200. <i>Rhinella ocellata</i> (Günther, 1858)	
201. <i>Rhinella ornata</i> (Spix, 1824)	
202. <i>Rhinella parecis</i> Ávila, Morais, Perez, Pansonato, Carvalho, Rojas, Gordo & Farias, 2020	recently described species
203. <i>Rhinella poeppigii</i> (Tschudi, 1845)	
204. <i>Rhinella proboscidea</i> (Spix, 1824)	
205. <i>Rhinella pygmaea</i> (Myers & Carvalho, 1952)	
206. <i>Rhinella rubescens</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
207. <i>Rhinella scitula</i> (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003)	
208. <i>Rhinella sebbeni</i> Vaz-Silva, Maciel, Bastos & Pombal, 2015	
209. <i>Rhinella veredas</i> (Brandão, Maciel & Sebben, 2007)	
Family Centrolenidae (Centroleninae)	3 gen, 9 spp
210. <i>Cochranella resplendens</i> (Lynch & Duellman, 1973)	new occurrence (Costa-Campos et al., 2020b)
211. <i>Teratohyla adenocheira</i> (Harvey & Noonan, 2005)	
212. <i>Teratohyla midas</i> (Lynch & Duellman, 1973)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
213. <i>Vitreorana baliomma</i> Pontes, Caramaschi & Pombal, 2014	
214. <i>Vitreorana eurygnatha</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
215. <i>Vitreorana franciscana</i> Santana, Barros, Pontes & Feio, 2015	
216. <i>Vitreorana parvula</i> (Boulenger, 1895)	
217. <i>Vitreorana ritae</i> (B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952)	
218. <i>Vitreorana uranoscopa</i> (Müller, 1924)	
Family Centrolenidae (Hyalinobatrachinae)	1 gen, 6 spp
219. <i>Hyalinobatrachium cappellei</i> (van Lidth de Jeude, 1904)	
220. <i>Hyalinobatrachium carlesvilai</i> Castroviejo-Fisher, Padial, Chaparro, Aguayo & De la Riva, 2009	
221. <i>Hyalinobatrachium iaspidiense</i> (Ayarzaüena, 1992)	
222. <i>Hyalinobatrachium mondolfi</i> Señaris & Ayarzagüena, 2001	
223. <i>Hyalinobatrachium muiiraquitan</i> Oliveira & Hernández-Ruz, 2017	
224. <i>Hyalinobatrachium munozorum</i> (Lynch & Duellman, 1973)	new spelling
225. <i>Hyalinobatrachium taylori</i> (Goin, 1968)	new occurrence (de Alves da Silva et al. 2020; Costa-Campos et al. 2021)
226. <i>Hyalinobatrachium tricolor</i> Castroviejo-Fisher, Vilà, Ayarzagüena, Blanc & Ernst, 2011	new occurrence (Costa-Campos et al. 2021)

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
Family Ceratophryidae	2 gen, 6 spp
227. <i>Ceratophrys aurita</i> (Raddi, 1823)	
228. <i>Ceratophrys cornuta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
229. <i>Ceratophrys cranwelli</i> Barrio, 1980	
230. <i>Ceratophrys joazeirensis</i> Mercadal de Barrio, 1986	
231. <i>Ceratophrys ornata</i> (Bell, 1843)	
232. <i>Lepidobatrachus asper</i> (Budgett, 1899)	
Family Craugastoridae (Ceuthomantinae)	2 gen, 44 spp
233. <i>Ceuthomantis cavernibardus</i> (Myers & Donnelly, 1997)	
234. <i>Pristimantis academicus</i> Lehr, Moravec & Gagliardi-Urrutia, 2010	
235. <i>Pristimantis acuminatus</i> (Schreve, 1935)	
236. <i>Pristimantis altamazonicus</i> (Barbour & Dunn, 1921)	
237. <i>Pristimantis aureolineatus</i> (Guayasamin, Ron, Cisneros- -Heredia, Lamar & McCracken, 2006)	
238. <i>Pristimantis buccinator</i> (Rodriguez, 1994)	
239. <i>Pristimantis carvalhoi</i> (B. Lutz in B. Lutz & Kloss, 1952)	
240. <i>Pristimantis chiastonotus</i> (Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
241. <i>Pristimantis conspicillatus</i> (Günther, 1858)	
242. <i>Pristimantis delius</i> (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995)	
243. <i>Pristimantis diadematus</i> (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875)	
244. <i>Pristimantis dundeei</i> (Heyer & Muñoz, 1999)	
245. <i>Pristimantis eurydactylus</i> (Hedges & Schlüter, 1992)	
246. <i>Pristimantis fenestratus</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
247. <i>Pristimantis giorgii</i> Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020	recently described species
248. <i>Pristimantis gutturalis</i> (Hoogmoed, Lynch & Lescure, 1977)	
249. <i>Pristimantis inguinalis</i> (Parker, 1940)	
250. <i>Pristimantis lacrimosus</i> (Jiménez de la Espada, 1875)	
251. <i>Pristimantis lanthanites</i> (Lynch, 1975)	
252. <i>Pristimantis latro</i> Oliveira, Rodrigues, Kaefer, Pinto & Hernández-Ruz, 2017	
253. <i>Pristimantis luscombei</i> (Duellman & Mendelson, 1995)	
254. <i>Pristimantis malkini</i> (Lynch, 1980)	
255. <i>Pristimantis marmoratus</i> (Boulenger, 1900)	
256. <i>Pristimantis martiae</i> (Lynch, 1974)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
267. <i>Pristimantis memorans</i> (Myers & Donnelly, 1997)	
258. <i>Pristimantis moa</i> Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020	recently described species
259. <i>Pristimantis ockendeni</i> (Boulenger, 1912)	
260. <i>Pristimantis orcus</i> Lehr, Catenazzi & Rodriguez, 2009	
261. <i>Pristimantis paulodutra</i> (Bokermann, 1975)	
262. <i>Pristimantis peruvianus</i> (Melin, 1941)	
263. <i>Pristimantis pictus</i> Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020	recently described species
264. <i>Pristimantis pluvian</i> Oliveira, Silva, Guimarães, Penhacek, Martínez, Rodrigues, Santana & Hernández-Ruíz, 2020	recently described species
265. <i>Pristimantis ramagii</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	
266. <i>Pristimantis reichlei</i> Padial & de La Riva, 2009	
267. <i>Pristimantis rupicola</i> Taucce, Nascimento, Trevisan, Leite, Santana, Haddad & Napoli, 2020	recently described species
268. <i>Pristimantis skydmainos</i> (Flores & Rodriguez, 1997)	
269. <i>Pristimantis toftae</i> (Duellman, 1978)	
270. <i>Pristimantis variabilis</i> (Lynch, 1968)	
271. <i>Pristimantis ventrigranulosus</i> Maciel, Vaz-Silva, Oliveira & Padial, 2012	
272. <i>Pristimantis ventrimarmoratus</i> (Boulenger, 1912)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
273. <i>Pristimantis vilarsi</i> (Melin, 1941)	
274. <i>Pristimantis vinhai</i> (Bokermann, 1975)	
275. <i>Pristimantis zeuctotylus</i> (Lynch & Hoogmoed, 1977)	
276. <i>Pristimantis zimmermanae</i> (Heyer & Hardy, 1991)	
Family Craugastoridae (Craugastorinae)	2 gen, 4 spp
277. <i>Haddadus aramunha</i> (Cassimiro, Verdade & Rodrigues, 2008)	
278. <i>Haddadus binotatus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
279. <i>Haddadus plicifer</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	
280. <i>Strabomantis sulcatus</i> (Cope, 1874)	
Family Craugastoridae (Holoadeninae)	6 gen, 16 spp
281. <i>Bahius bilineatus</i> (Bokermann, 1975)	recently described genus (Dubois et al., 2021)
282. <i>Barycholos ternetzi</i> (Miranda Ribeiro, 1937)	
283. <i>Euparkerella brasiliensis</i> (Parker, 1926)	
284. <i>Euparkerella cochranae</i> Izecksohn, 1988	
285. <i>Euparkerella cryptica</i> Hepp, S. Carvalho-e-Silva, A. Carvalho-e-Silva & Folly, 2015	
286. <i>Euparkerella robusta</i> Izecksohn, 1988	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
287. <i>Euparkerella tridactyla</i> Izecksohn, 1988	
288. <i>Holoaden bradei</i> B. Lutz, 1958	
289. <i>Holoaden luederwaldti</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920	
290. <i>Holoaden pholeter</i> Pombal, Siqueira, Dorigo, Vrcibradic & Rocha, 2008	
291. <i>Holoaden suarezi</i> Martins & Zaher, 2013	
292. <i>Noblella myrmecoides</i> (Lynch, 1976)	
293. <i>Oreobates antrum</i> Vaz-Silva, Maciel, Andrade & Amaro, 2018	
294. <i>Oreobates heterodactylus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
295. <i>Oreobates quixensis</i> Jiménez de la Espada, 1872	
296. <i>Oreobates remotus</i> Teixeira, Amaro, Recoder, Sena & Rodrigues, 2012	
Family Cycloramphidae	2 gen, 36 spp
297. <i>Cycloramphus acangatan</i> Verdade & Rodrigues, 2003	
298. <i>Cycloramphus asper</i> Werner, 1899	
299. <i>Cycloramphus bandeirensis</i> Heyer, 1983	
300. <i>Cycloramphus bolitoglossus</i> (Werner, 1897)	
301. <i>Cycloramphus boraceiensis</i> Heyer, 1983	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
302. <i>Cycloramphus brasiliensis</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
303. <i>Cycloramphus carvalhoi</i> (Izecksohn, 1983)	new status
304. <i>Cycloramphus heyeri</i>	nomen novum pro <i>Cycloramphus carvalhoi</i> Heyer, 1983
305. <i>Cycloramphus catarinensis</i> Heyer, 1983	
306. <i>Cycloramphus cedrensis</i> Heyer, 1983	
307. <i>Cycloramphus diringshofeni</i> Bokermann, 1957	
308. <i>Cycloramphus dubius</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
309. <i>Cycloramphus duseni</i> (Andersson, 1914)	
310. <i>Cycloramphus eleutherodactylus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
311. <i>Cycloramphus faustoi</i> Brasileiro, Haddad, Sawaya & Sazima, 2007	
312. <i>Cycloramphus fuliginosus</i> Tschudi, 1838	
313. <i>Cycloramphus granulatus</i> A. Lutz, 1929	
314. <i>Cycloramphus izecksohni</i> Heyer, 1983	
315. <i>Cycloramphus juimirim</i> Haddad & Sazima, 1989	
316. <i>Cycloramphus lithomimeticus</i> Silva & Ouverney, 2012	
317. <i>Cycloramphus lutzorum</i> Heyer, 1983	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
318. <i>Cycloramphus migueli</i> Heyer, 1988	
319. <i>Cycloramphus mirandaribeiroi</i> Heyer, 1983	
320. <i>Cycloramphus ohausi</i> (Wandolleck, 1907)	
321. <i>Cycloramphus organensis</i> Weber, Verdade, Salles, Fouquet & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2011	
322. <i>Cycloramphus parvulus</i> (Girard, 1853)	new status
323. <i>Cycloramphus rhyakonastes</i> Heyer, 1983	
324. <i>Cycloramphus semipalmatus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
325. <i>Cycloramphus stejnegeri</i> (Noble, 1924)	
326. <i>Cycloramphus valae</i> Heyer, 1983	
327. <i>Thoropa lutzi</i> Cochran, 1938	
328. <i>Thoropa megatympanum</i> Caramaschi & Sazima, 1984	
329. <i>Thoropa miliaris</i> (Spix, 1824)	
330. <i>Thoropa petropolitana</i> (Wandolleck, 1907)	
331. <i>Thoropa saxatilis</i> Crocoft & Heyer, 1988	
332. <i>Thoropa taophora</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923)	
Family Dendrobatidae (Colostethinae)	1 gen, 10 spp
333. <i>Ameerega berohoka</i> Vaz-Silva & Maciel, 2011	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
334. <i>Ameerega braccata</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
335. <i>Ameerega flavopicta</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
336. <i>Ameerega hahneli</i> (Boulenger, 1884)	
337. <i>Ameerega macero</i> (Rodriguez & Myers, 1993)	
338. <i>Ameerega munduruku</i> Neves, Silva, Akieda, Cabrera, Koroiva & Santana, 2017	
339. <i>Ameerega petersi</i> (Silverstone, 1976)	
340. <i>Ameerega picta</i> (Bibron in Tschudi, 1838)	
341. <i>Ameerega pulchripecta</i> (Silverstone, 1976)	
342. <i>Ameerega trivittata</i> (Spix, 1824)	
Family Dendrobatidae (Dendrobatinae)	3 gen, 12 spp
343. <i>Adelphobates castaneoticus</i> (Caldwell & Myers, 1990)	
344. <i>Adelphobates galactonotus</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
345. <i>Adelphobates quinquevittatus</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
346. <i>Dendrobates leucomelas</i> Steindachner, 1864	
3547 <i>Dendrobates tinctorius</i> (Cuvier, 1797)	
348. <i>Ranitomeya amazonica</i> (Schulte, 1999)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
349. <i>Ranitomeya defleri</i> Twomey & Brown, 2009	
350. <i>Ranitomeya sirensis</i> (Aichinger, 1991)	
351. <i>Ranitomeya toraro</i> Brown, Caldwell, Twomey, Melo-Sampaio & Souza, 2011	
352. <i>Ranitomeya uakarii</i> Brown, Schulte & Summers, 2006	
353. <i>Ranitomeya vanzolinii</i> (Myers, 1982)	
354. <i>Ranitomeya variabilis</i> (Zimmermann & Zimmermann, 1988)	
Family Dendrobatidae (Hyloxalinae)	1 gen, 1 sp
355. <i>Hyloxalus chlorocraspedus</i> (Caldwell, 2005)	
Family Eleutherodactylidae (Eleutherodactylinae)	1 gen, 1 sp
356. <i>Eleutherodactylus johnstonei</i> Barbour, 1914	invasive species
Family Eleutherodactylidae (Phyzelaphryninae)	2 gen, 12 sp
357. <i>Adelophryne adiaistola</i> Hoogmoed & Lescure, 1984	
358. <i>Adelophryne amapaensis</i> Taucce, Costa-Campos, Haddad & Carvalho, 2020	recently described species
359. <i>Adelophryne baturitensis</i> Hoogmoed, Borges & Cascon, 1994	
360. <i>Adelophryne glandulata</i> Lourenço-de-Moraes, Ferreira, Fouquet & Bastos, 2014	
361. <i>Adelophryne gutturosa</i> Hoogmoed & Lescure, 1984	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
362. <i>Adelophryne maranguapensis</i> Hoogmoed, Borges & Cascon, 1994	
363. <i>Adelophryne meridionalis</i> Santana, Fonseca, Neves & Carvalho, 2012	
364. <i>Adelophryne michelin</i> Lourenço-de-Moraes, Dias, Mira-Mendes, Oliveira, Barth, Ruas, Vences, Solé & Bastos, 2018	
365. <i>Adelophryne mucronata</i> Lourenço-de-Moraes, Solé & Toledo, 2012	
366. <i>Adelophryne pachydactyla</i> Hoogmoed, Borges & Cascon, 1994	
367. <i>Phyzelaphryne miriamae</i> Heyer, 1977	
368. <i>Phyzelaphryne nimio</i> Simões, Costa, Rojas-Runjaic, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Sturaro, Peloso & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2018	
Family Hemiphractidae	5 gen, 21 spp
369. <i>Alainia albolineata</i> (Lutz & Lutz, 1939)	new status
370. <i>Alainia ernestoi</i> (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920)	new status
371. <i>Alainia fulvorufa</i> (Andersson, 1911)	new status
372. <i>Alainia microdiscus</i> (Andersson in Lönnberg & Andersson, 1910)	new status
373. <i>Eothecca fissipes</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	new status
374. <i>Eothecca flamma</i> Juncá & Nunes, 2008	new status
375. <i>Eothecca megacephala</i> Izecksohn, S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 2009	new status

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
376. <i>Eothecca prasina</i> Teixeira, Dal Vechio, Recoder, Carnaval, Strangas, Damasceno, Sena & Rodrigues, 2012	new status
377. <i>Eothecca pulchra</i> Caramaschi & Rodrigues, 2007	new status
378. <i>Eothecca recava</i> Teixeira, Dal Vechio, Recoder, Carnaval, Strangas, Damasceno, Sena & Rodrigues, 2012	new status
379. <i>Fritziana fissilis</i> (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920)	
380. <i>Fritziana goeldii</i> (Boulenger, 1895)	
381. <i>Fritziana izecksohni</i> Folly, Hepp & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2018	
382. <i>Fritziana mitus</i> Walker, Wachlevski, Nogueira-Costa, Garcia & Haddad, 2018	
383. <i>Fritziana ohausi</i> (Wandolleck, 1907)	
384. <i>Fritziana tonimi</i> Walker, Gasparini & Haddad, 2016	
385. <i>Fritziana ulei</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
386. <i>Hemiphractus helioi</i> Sheil & Mendelson, 2001	
387. <i>Hemiphractus scutatus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
388. <i>Stefania neblinae</i> Carvalho, MacCulloch, Bonora & Vogt, 2010	
389. <i>Stefania tamacuarina</i> Myers & Donnelly, 1997	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
Family Hylidae	1 gen, 1 sp
390. <i>"Hyla" imitator</i> (Barbour & Dunn, 1921)	<i>Incertae sedis</i>
Family Hylidae (Cophomantinae)	3 gen, 111 spp
391. <i>Aplastodiscus albofrenatus</i> (A. Lutz, 1924)	
392. <i>Aplastodiscus albosignatus</i> (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938)	
393. <i>Aplastodiscus arildae</i> (Cruz & Peixoto, 1987)	
394. <i>Aplastodiscus cavicola</i> (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985)	
395. <i>Aplastodiscus cochranae</i> (Mertens, 1952)	
396. <i>Aplastodiscus ehrhardti</i> (Müller, 1924)	
397. <i>Aplastodiscus eugenioi</i> (A. Carvalho-e-Silva & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2005)	
398. <i>Aplastodiscus flumineus</i> (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985)	
399. <i>Aplastodiscus heterophonicus</i> Pinheiro, Pezzuti, Berneck, Lyra, Lima & Leite, 2021	recently described species
400. <i>Aplastodiscus ibirapitanga</i> (Cruz, Pimenta & Silvano, 2003)	
401. <i>Aplastodiscus leucopygius</i> (Cruz & Peixoto, 1985)	
402. <i>Aplastodiscus lutzorum</i> Berneck, Giaretta, Brandão, Cruz & Haddad, 2017	
403. <i>Aplastodiscus musicus</i> (B. Lutz, 1949)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
404. <i>Aplastodiscus perviridis</i> B. Lutz, 1950	
405. <i>Aplastodiscus sibilatus</i> (Cruz, Pimenta & Silvano, 2003)	
406. <i>Aplastodiscus weygoldti</i> (Cruz & Peixoto, 1987)	
407. <i>Boana albomarginata</i> (Spix, 1824)	
408. <i>Boana albopunctata</i> (Spix, 1824)	
409. <i>Boana alfaroi</i> (Caminer & Ron, 2014)	new occurrence (Caminer & Ron, 2014)
410. <i>Boana appendiculata</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	recently revalidated species (Caminer & Ron, 2020)
411. <i>Boana atlantica</i> (Caramaschi & Velosa, 1996)	
412. <i>Boana benitezi</i> (Rivero, 1961)	
413. <i>Boana bischoffi</i> (Boulenger, 1887)	
414. <i>Boana boans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
415. <i>Boana botumirim</i> (Caramaschi, Cruz & Nascimento, 2009)	
416. <i>Boana buriti</i> (Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999)	
417. <i>Boana caiapo</i> Pinheiro, Cintra, Valdujo, Silva, Martins, Silva & Garcia, 2018	
418. <i>Boana caingua</i> (Carrizo, 1991)	
419. <i>Boana caipora</i> (Antunes, Faivovich & Haddad, 2008)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
420. <i>Boana calcarata</i> (Troschel in Schomburgk, 1848)	
421. <i>Boana cambui</i> (Pinheiro, Pezzuti, Leite, Garcia, Haddad & Faivovich, 2016)	
422. <i>Boana cinerascens</i> (Spix, 1824)	
423. <i>Boana cipoensis</i> (B. Lutz, 1968)	
424. <i>Boana claresignata</i> (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939)	new status (Lyra et al., 2020)
425. <i>Boana clepsydra</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	new status (Lyra et al., 2020)
426. <i>Boana crepitans</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1824)	
427. <i>Boana curupi</i> (Garcia, Faivovich & Haddad, 2007)	
428. <i>Boana cymbalum</i> (Bokerman, 1963)	
429. <i>Boana dentei</i> (Bokermann, 1967)	
430. <i>Boana diabolica</i> (Fouquet, Martinez, Zeidler, Courtois, Gaucher, Blanc, Lima, Souza, Rodrigues & Kok, 2016)	
431. <i>Boana ericae</i> (Caramaschi & Cruz, 2000)	
432. <i>Boana exastis</i> (Caramaschi & Rodriguez, 2003)	
433. <i>Boana faber</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1821)	
434. <i>Boana fasciata</i> (Günther, 1858)	
435. <i>Boana freicanecae</i> (Carnaval & Peixoto, 2004)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
436. <i>Boana geographica</i> (Spix, 1824)	
437. <i>Boana goiana</i> (B. Lutz, 1968)	
438. <i>Boana gracilis</i> (Melin, 1941)	new occurrence (Sturaro et al., 2020)
439. <i>Boana guentheri</i> (Boulenger, 1886)	
440. <i>Boana hobbsi</i> (Cochran & Goin, 1970)	
441. <i>Boana icamiaba</i> Peloso, Oliveira, Sturaro, Rodrigues, Lima, Bitar, Wheeler & Aleixo, 2018	
442. <i>Boana jaguariaivensis</i> (Caramaschi, Cruz & Segalla, 2010)	
443. <i>Boana joaquini</i> (Lutz, 1968)	
444. <i>Boana lanciformis</i> (Cope, 1871)	
445. <i>Boana leptolineata</i> (P. Braun & C. Braun, 1977)	
446. <i>Boana leucocheila</i> (Caramaschi & Niemeyer, 2003)	
447. <i>Boana lundii</i> (Burmeister, 1856)	
448. <i>Boana maculateralis</i> (Caminer & Ron, 2014)	
449. <i>Boana marginata</i> (Boulenger, 1887)	
450. <i>Boana microderma</i> (Pyburn, 1977)	
451. <i>Boana multifasciata</i> (Günther, 1859)	
452. <i>Boana nympha</i> (Faivovich, Moravec, Cisneros-Heredia & Köhler, 2006)	

ORDER ANURA

STATUS

453. *Boana ornatissima* (Noble, 1923)
454. *Boana paranaiba* (Carvalho, Giaretta & Facure, 2010)
455. *Boana pardalis* (Spix, 1824)
456. *Boana poaju* (Garcia, Peixoto & Haddad, 2008)
457. *Boana polytaenia* (Cope, 1870)
458. *Boana pombali* (Caramaschi, Pimenta & Feio, 2004)
459. *Boana prasina* (Burmeister, 1856)
460. *Boana pulchella* (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)
461. *Boana punctata* (Schneider, 1799)
462. *Boana raniceps* (Cope, 1862)
463. *Boana secedens* (B. Lutz, 1963)
464. *Boana semiguttata* (A. Lutz, 1925)
465. *Boana semilineata* (Spix, 1824)
466. *Boana stellae* (Kwet, 2008)
467. *Boana stenocephala* (Caramaschi & Cruz, 1999)
468. *Boana tepuniana* (Barrio-Amoros & Brewer-Carias, 2008)

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
469. <i>Boana ventrimaculata</i> Caminer & Ron, 2020	recently described species
470. <i>Boana wavrini</i> (Parker, 1936)	
471. <i>Boana xerophyla</i> (Dumeril & Bibron, 1841)	
472. <i>Bokermannohyla ahenea</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2004)	
473. <i>Bokermannohyla alvarengai</i> (Bokermann, 1956)	
474. <i>Bokermannohyla astartea</i> (Bokermann, 1977)	
475. <i>Bokermannohyla capra</i> Napoli & Pimenta, 2009	
476. <i>Bokermannohyla caramaschii</i> (Napoli, 2005)	
477. <i>Bokermannohyla carvalhoi</i> (Peixoto, 1981)	
478. <i>Bokermannohyla circumdata</i> (Cope, 1871)	
479. <i>Bokermannohyla diamantina</i> Napoli & Juncá, 2006	
480. <i>Bokermannohyla flavopicta</i> Leite, Pezzuti & Garcia, 2012	
481. <i>Bokermannohyla gouveai</i> (Peixoto & Cruz, 1992)	
482. <i>Bokermannohyla hylax</i> (Heyer, 1985)	
483. <i>Bokermannohyla ibitiguara</i> (Cardoso, 1983)	
484. <i>Bokermannohyla ibitipoca</i> (Caramaschi & Feio, 1990)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
485. <i>Bokermannohyla itapoty</i> Lugli & Haddad, 2006	
486. <i>Bokermannohyla izecksohni</i> (Jim & Caramaschi, 1979)	
487. <i>Bokermannohyla juiju</i> Faivovich, Lugli, Lourenço & Haddad, 2009	
488. <i>Bokermannohyla langei</i> (Bokermann, 1965)	
489. <i>Bokermannohyla lucianae</i> (Napoli & Pimenta, 2003)	
490. <i>Bokermannohyla luctuosa</i> (Pombal & Haddad, 1993)	
491. <i>Bokermannohyla martinsi</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	
492. <i>Bokermannohyla nanuzae</i> (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973)	
493. <i>Bokermannohyla napolii</i> Carvalho, Giaretta & Magrini, 2012	
494. <i>Bokermannohyla oxente</i> Lugli & Haddad, 2006	
495. <i>Bokermannohyla pseudopseudis</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
496. <i>Bokermannohyla ravidia</i> (Caramaschi, Napoli & Bernardes, 2001)	
497. <i>Bokermannohyla sagarana</i> Leite, Pezzuti & Drummond, 2011	
498. <i>Bokermannohyla sapiranga</i> Brandão, Magalhães, Garda, Campos, Sebben & Maciel, 2012	
499. <i>Bokermannohyla saxicola</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	
500. <i>Bokermannohyla sazimai</i> (Cardoso & Andrade, 1982)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
501. <i>Bokermannohyla vulcaniae</i> (Vasconcelos & Giaretta, 2005)	
Family Hylidae (Dendropsophinae)	2 gen, 73 spp
502. <i>Dendropsophus acreanus</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	
503. <i>Dendropsophus anataliasiasi</i> (Bokermann, 1972)	
504. <i>Dendropsophus anceps</i> (A. Lutz, 1929)	
505. <i>Dendropsophus araguaya</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998)	
506. <i>Dendropsophus berthallutzae</i> (Bokermann, 1962)	
507. <i>Dendropsophus bifurcus</i> (Andersson, 1945)	
508. <i>Dendropsophus bilobatus</i> Ferrão, Moravec, Hanken & Lima, 2020	recently described species
509. <i>Dendropsophus bipunctatus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
510. <i>Dendropsophus bokermanni</i> (Goin, 1960)	
511. <i>Dendropsophus branneri</i> (Cochran, 1948)	
512. <i>Dendropsophus brevifrons</i> (Duellman & Crump, 1974)	
513. <i>Dendropsophus bromeliaceus</i> Ferreira, Faivovich, Beard & Pombal, 2015	
514. <i>Dendropsophus cachimbo</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999)	
515. <i>Dendropsophus cerradensis</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1998)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
516. <i>Dendropsophus counani</i> Fouquet, Orrico, Ernst, Blanc, Martinez, Vacher, Rodrigues, Ouboter, Jairam & Ron, 2015	
517. <i>Dendropsophus cruzi</i> (Pombal & Bastos, 1998)	
518. <i>Dendropsophus decipiens</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
519. <i>Dendropsophus dutrai</i> (Gomes & Peixoto, 1996)	
520. <i>Dendropsophus elegans</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1824)	
521. <i>Dendropsophus elianeae</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 2000)	
522. <i>Dendropsophus gaucheri</i> (Lescure & Marty, 2000)	
523. <i>Dendropsophus giesleri</i> (Mertens, 1950)	
524. <i>Dendropsophus haddadi</i> (Bastos & Pombal, 1996)	
525. <i>Dendropsophus haraldschultzi</i> (Bokermann, 1962)	
526. <i>Dendropsophus jimi</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999)	
527. <i>Dendropsophus joannae</i> (Köhler & Lötters, 2001)	new occurrence (Melo-Sampaio & Souza, 2015)
528. <i>Dendropsophus kamagarini</i> Rivadeneira, Venegas & Ron, 2018	
529. <i>Dendropsophus koechlini</i> (Duellman & Trueb, 1989)	
530. <i>Dendropsophus leali</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	
531. <i>Dendropsophus leucophyllatus</i> (Beireis, 1783)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
532. <i>Dendropsophus limai</i> (Bokermann, 1962)	
533. <i>Dendropsophus mapinguari</i> Peloso, Orrico, Haddad, Lima-Filho & Sturaro, 2016	
534. <i>Dendropsophus marmoratus</i> (Laurenti, 1768)	
535. <i>Dendropsophus melanargyreus</i> (Cope, 1887)	
536. <i>Dendropsophus meridianus</i> (B. Lutz, 1954)	
537. <i>Dendropsophus microcephalus</i> (Cope, 1886)	
538. <i>Dendropsophus microps</i> (Peter, 1872)	
539. <i>Dendropsophus minimus</i> (Ahl, 1933)	
540. <i>Dendropsophus minusculus</i> (Rivero, 1971)	
541. <i>Dendropsophus minutus</i> (Peters, 1872)	
542. <i>Dendropsophus miyatai</i> (Vigle & Goberdhan-Vigle, 1990)	
543. <i>Dendropsophus nahdereri</i> (B. Lutz & Bokermann, 1963)	
544. <i>Dendropsophus nanus</i> (Boulenger, 1889)	
545. <i>Dendropsophus nekronastes</i> Dias, Haddad, Argôlo & Orrico, 2017	
546. <i>Dendropsophus novaisi</i> (Bokermann, 1968)	
547. <i>Dendropsophus oliveirai</i> (Bokermann, 1963)	
548. <i>Dendropsophus ozzyi</i> Orrico, Peloso, Sturaro, Silva, Neckel-Oliveira, Gordo, Faivovich & Haddad, 2014	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
549. <i>Dendropsophus parviceps</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	
550. <i>Dendropsophus pauiniensis</i> (Heyer, 1977)	
551. <i>Dendropsophus pseudomeridianus</i> (Cruz, Caramaschi & Dias, 2000)	
552. <i>Dendropsophus reticulatus</i> (Jimenez de la Espada, 1870)	
553. <i>Dendropsophus rhea</i> (Napoli & Caramaschi, 1999)	
554. <i>Dendropsophus rhodopeplus</i> (Günther, 1858)	
555. <i>Dendropsophus riveroi</i> (Cochran & Goin, 1970)	
556. <i>Dendropsophus rossalleni</i> (Goin, 1959)	
557. <i>Dendropsophus rubicundulus</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
558. <i>Dendropsophus ruschii</i> (Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1987)	
559. <i>Dendropsophus salli</i> Jungfer, Reichle & Piskurek, 2010	new occurrence (Melo-Sampaio & Souza, 2015)
560. <i>Dendropsophus sanborni</i> (Schmidt, 1944)	
561. <i>Dendropsophus sarayacuensis</i> (Shreve, 1935)	
562. <i>Dendropsophus schubarti</i> (Bokermann, 1963)	
563. <i>Dendropsophus seniculus</i> (Cope, 1868)	
564. <i>Dendropsophus soaresi</i> (Caramaschi & Jim, 1983)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
565. <i>Dendropsophus studerae</i> (S. Carvalho-e-Silva, A. Carvalho-e-Silva & Izecksohn, 2003)	
566. <i>Dendropsophus timbeba</i> (Martins & Cardoso, 1987)	
567. <i>Dendropsophus tintinnabulum</i> (Melin, 1941)	
568. <i>Dendropsophus triangulum</i> (Günther, 1869)	
569. <i>Dendropsophus tritaeniatus</i> (Bokermann, 1965)	
570. <i>Dendropsophus walfordi</i> (Bokermann, 1962)	
571. <i>Dendropsophus wernerii</i> (Cochran, 1952)	
572. <i>Dendropsophus xapuriensis</i> (Martins & Cardoso, 1987)	
573. <i>Xenohyla eugenioi</i> Caramaschi, 1998	
574. <i>Xenohyla truncata</i> (Izecksohn, 1959)	
Family Hylidae (Lophohylineae)	8 gen, 52 spp
575. <i>Corythomantis botoque</i> Marques, Haddad, & Garda, 2021	recently described species
576. <i>Corythomantis greeningi</i> Boulenger, 1896	
577. <i>Dryaderces inframaculata</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	new spelling
578. <i>Dryaderces pearsoni</i> (Gauge, 1929)	
579. <i>Itapotihyla langsdorffii</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
580. <i>Nyctimantis arapapa</i> (Pimenta, Napoli & Haddad, 2009)	new status (Blotto et al., 2021)
581. <i>Nyctimantis bokermanni</i> (Pombal, 1993)	new status (Blotto et al., 2021)
582. <i>Nyctimantis brunoi</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	new status (Blotto et al., 2021)
583. <i>Nyctimantis pomba</i> Assis, Santana, da Silva, Quintela & Feio, 2013	new status (Blotto et al., 2021)
584. <i>Nyctimantis galeata</i> Pombal, Menezes, Fontes, Nunes, Rocha & Van Sluys, 2012	new status (Blotto et al., 2021)
585. <i>Osteocephalus buckleyi</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	
586. <i>Osteocephalus cabrerai</i> (Cochran & Goin, 1970)	
587. <i>Osteocephalus camufatus</i> Jungfer, Verdade, Faivovich & Rodrigues, 2016	
588. <i>Osteocephalus castaneicola</i> Moravec, Aparicio, Guerrero-Reinhard, Calderón, Jungfer & Gvoždík, 2009	
589. <i>Osteocephalus deridens</i> Jungfer, Ron, Seipp & Almendáriz, 2000	
590. <i>Osteocephalus helenae</i> (Ruthven, 1919)	
591. <i>Osteocephalus leprieurii</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	
592. <i>Osteocephalus oophagus</i> Jungfer & Schiesari, 1995	
593. <i>Osteocephalus planiceps</i> Cope, 1874	
594. <i>Osteocephalus subtilis</i> Martins & Cardoso, 1987	
595. <i>Osteocephalus taurinus</i> Steindachner, 1862	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
596. <i>Osteocephalus vilarsi</i> (Melin, 1941)	
597. <i>Phyllodytes acuminatus</i> Bokermann, 1966	
598. <i>Phyllodytes amadoi</i> Vörös, Dias & Solé, 2017	
599. <i>Phyllodytes brevirostris</i> Peixoto & Cruz, 1988	
600. <i>Phyllodytes edelmoi</i> Peixoto, Caramaschi & Freire, 2003	
601. <i>Phyllodytes gyrinaethes</i> Peixoto, Caramaschi & Freire, 2003	
602. <i>Phyllodytes kautskyi</i> Peixoto & Cruz, 1988	
603. <i>Phyllodytes luteolus</i> Wied-Neuwied, 1824	
604. <i>Phyllodytes maculosus</i> Cruz, Feio & Cardoso, 2007	
605. <i>Phyllodytes magnus</i> Dias, Novaes-e-Fagundes, Neto, Zina, Garcia, Recoder, Dal Vechio, Rodrigues & Solé, 2020	recently described species
606. <i>Phyllodytes megatympanum</i> Marciano, Lantyer-Silva & Solé, 2017	
607. <i>Phyllodytes melanomystax</i> Caramaschi, Silva & Britto-Pereira, 1992	
608. <i>Phyllodytes praeceptor</i> Orrico, Dias & Marciano, 2018	
609. <i>Phyllodytes punctatus</i> Caramaschi & Peixoto, 2004	
610. <i>Phyllodytes tuberculatus</i> Bokermann, 1966	
611. <i>Phyllodytes wuchereri</i> (Peters, 1873)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
612. <i>Tepuihyla shushupe</i> Ron, Venegas, Ortega-Andrade, Gagliardi-Urrutia & Salerno, 2016	
613. <i>Trachycephalus atlas</i> Bokermann, 1966	
614. <i>Trachycephalus coriaceus</i> (Peters, 1867)	
615. <i>Trachycephalus cunauaru</i> Gordo, Toledo, Suárez, Kawashita-Ribeiro, Ávila, Morais & Nunes, 2013	
616. <i>Trachycephalus dibernardoii</i> Kwet & Solé, 2008	
617. <i>Trachycephalus hadroceps</i> (Duellman & Hoogmoed, 1992)	
618. <i>Trachycephalus helioi</i> Nunes, Suárez, Gordo & Pombal, 2013	
619. <i>Trachycephalus imitatrix</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
620. <i>Trachycephalus lepidus</i> (Pombal, Haddad & Cruz, 2003)	
621. <i>Trachycephalus mambaiensis</i> Cintra, Silva, Silva, Garcia & Zaher, 2009	
622. <i>Trachycephalus mesophaeus</i> (Hensel, 1867)	
623. <i>Trachycephalus nigromaculatus</i> Tschudi, 1838	
624. <i>Trachycephalus resinifictrix</i> (Goeldi, 1907)	
625. <i>Trachycephalus typhonius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
626. <i>Trachycephalus venezolanus</i> (Mertens, 1950)	new status (Blotto et al., 2021)

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
Family Hylidae (Pseudinae)	3 gen, 12 spp
627. <i>Lysapsus bolivianus</i> Gallardo, 1961	
628. <i>Lysapsus caraya</i> Gallardo, 1964	
629. <i>Lysapsus laevis</i> (Parker, 1935)	
630. <i>Lysapsus limellum</i> Cope, 1862	
631. <i>Pseudis bolbodactyla</i> A. Lutz, 1925	
632. <i>Pseudis cardosoi</i> Kwet, 2000	
633. <i>Pseudis fusca</i> Garman, 1883	
634. <i>Pseudis minuta</i> Günther, 1858	
635. <i>Pseudis paradoxa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
636. <i>Pseudis platensis</i> Gallardo, 1961	
637. <i>Pseudis tocantins</i> Caramaschi & Cruz, 1998	
638. <i>Scarthyla goinorum</i> (Bokermann, 1962)	
Family Hylidae (Scinaxinae)	3 gen, 125 spp
639. <i>Gabohyla pauloalvini</i> (Bokermann, 1973)	recently described genus (Araujo-Vieira et al., 2020)
640. <i>Scinax acuminatus</i> (Cope, 1862)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
641. <i>Scinax agilis</i> (Cruz & Peixoto, 1983)	new status
642. <i>Scinax albicans</i> (Bokermann, 1967)	new status
643. <i>Scinax alcatraz</i> (B. Lutz, 1973)	new status
644. <i>Scinax alter</i> (B. Lutz, 1973)	
645. <i>Scinax angrensis</i> (B. Lutz, 1973)	new status
646. <i>Scinax arduous</i> Peixoto, 2002	new status
647. <i>Scinax argyreornatus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	new status
648. <i>Scinax ariadne</i> (Bokermann, 1967)	new status
649. <i>Scinax aromothyella</i> Faivovich, 2005	new status
650. <i>Scinax atratus</i> (Peixoto, 1989)	new status
651. <i>Scinax auratus</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1821)	
652. <i>Scinax baumgardneri</i> (Rivero, 1961)	
653. <i>Scinax belloni</i> Faivoivch, Gasparini & Haddad, 2010	new status
654. <i>Scinax berthae</i> (Barrio, 1962)	new status
655. <i>Scinax boesemani</i> (Goin, 1966)	
656. <i>Scinax brieni</i> (De Witte, 1930)	new status

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
657. <i>Scinax cabralensis</i> Drummond, Baêta & Pires, 2007	
658. <i>Scinax caissara</i> Lourenço, Zina, Catroli, Kasahara, Faivovich & Haddad, 2016	new status
659. <i>Scinax caldarum</i> (B. Lutz, 1968)	
660. <i>Scinax camposseabrai</i> (Bokermann, 1968)	
661. <i>Scinax canastrensis</i> (Cardoso & Haddad, 1982)	new status
662. <i>Scinax cardosoi</i> (S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991)	
663. <i>Scinax carnevallii</i> (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989)	new status
664. <i>Scinax catharinae</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	new status
665. <i>Scinax centralis</i> Pombal & Bastos, 1996	new status
666. <i>Scinax constrictus</i> Lima, Bastos & Giaretta, 2004	
667. <i>Scinax cosenzai</i> Lacerda, Peixoto & Feio, 2012	new status
668. <i>Scinax cretatus</i> Nunes & Pombal, 2011	
669. <i>Scinax crospedospilus</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
670. <i>Scinax cruentomma</i> (Duellman, 1972)	new spelling
671. <i>Scinax curicica</i> Pugliesse, Pombal & Sazima, 2004	
672. <i>Scinax cuspidatus</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
673. <i>Scinax dolloi</i> (Werner, 1903)	
674. <i>Scinax duartei</i> (B. Lutz, 1951)	
675. <i>Scinax eurydice</i> (Bokermann, 1968)	
676. <i>Scinax exiguus</i> (Duellman, 1986)	
6797 <i>Scinax faivovich</i> Brasileiro, Oyamaguchi & Haddad, 2007	new status
678. <i>Scinax feioi</i> Lourenço, Lacerda, Cruz, Nascimento & Pombal, 2020	recently described species
679. <i>Scinax flavoguttatus</i> (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939)	new status
680. <i>Scinax fontanarrosai</i> Baldo, Araujo-Vieira, Cardozo, Borteiro, Leal, Pereyra, Kolenc, Lyra, Garcia, Haddad & Faivovich, 2019	recently described species
681. <i>Scinax funereus</i> (Cope, 1874)	
682. <i>Scinax fuscomarginatus</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
683. <i>Scinax fuscovarius</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
684. <i>Scinax garbei</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
685. <i>Scinax garibaldiae</i> Lourenço, Lingnau, Haddad & Faivovich, 2019	recently described species
686. <i>Scinax goya</i> (Andrade, Santos, Rocha, Pombal & Vaz-Silva, 2018)	new status
687. <i>Scinax granulatus</i> (Peters, 1871)	
688. <i>Scinax haddadorum</i> Araujo-Vieira, Valdujo & Faivovich, 2016	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
689. <i>Scinax hayii</i> (Barbour, 1909)	
690. <i>Scinax heyeri</i> (Peixoto & Weygoldt, 1986)	new status
691. <i>Scinax hiemalis</i> (Haddad & Pombal, 1987)	new status
692. <i>Scinax humilis</i> (B. Lutz, 1954)	new status
693. <i>Scinax ictericus</i> Duellman & Wiens, 1993	new occurrence (Melo-Sampaio & Souza, 2015)
694. <i>Scinax imbegue</i> Nunes, Kwet & Pombal, 2012	
695. <i>Scinax insperatus</i> Silva & Alves-Silva, 2011	new status
696. <i>Scinax iquitum</i> Moravec, Tuanama, Perez-Pena & Lehr, 2009	
697. <i>Scinax juncae</i> Nunes & Pombal, 2010	
698. <i>Scinax jureia</i> (Pombal & Gordo, 1991)	new status
699. <i>Scinax kautskyi</i> S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Peixoto, 1991	new status
700. <i>Scinax lindsayi</i> Pyburn, 1992	
701. <i>Scinax littoralis</i> (Pombal & Gordo, 1991)	new status
702. <i>Scinax littoreus</i> (Peixoto, 1988)	new status
703. <i>Scinax longilineus</i> (B. Lutz, 1968)	new status
704. <i>Scinax luizotavioi</i> (Caramaschi & Kisteumacher, 1989)	new status
705. <i>Scinax machadoi</i> (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973)	new status

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
706. <i>Scinax madeirae</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	
707. <i>Scinax maracaya</i> (Cardoso & Sazima, 1980)	
708. <i>Scinax melanodactylus</i> Lourenço, Luna & Pombal, 2014	new status
709. <i>Scinax melloi</i> (Peixoto, 1989)	new status
710. <i>Scinax montivagus</i> Juncá, Napoli, Nunes, Mercês & Abreu, 2015	
711. <i>Scinax muriciensis</i> Cruz, Nunes & Lima, 2011	new status
712. <i>Scinax nasicus</i> (Cope, 1862)	
713. <i>Scinax nebulosus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
714. <i>Scinax obtriangulatus</i> (B. Lutz, 1973)	new status
715. <i>Scinax onca</i> Ferrão, Moravec, Fraga, Pinheiro de Almeida, Kaefer & Lima, 2017	
716. <i>Scinax pachycrus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
717. <i>Scinax pedromedinae</i> (Henle, 1991)	
718. <i>Scinax peixotoi</i> Brasileiro, Haddad, Sawaya & Martins, 2007	new status
719. <i>Scinax perereca</i> Pombal, Haddad & Kasahara, 1995	
720. <i>Scinax perpusillus</i> (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1939)	new status
721. <i>Scinax pinimus</i> (Bokermann & Sazima, 1973)	new status

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
722. <i>Scinax pombali</i> Lourenço, Carvalho, Baeta, Pezzuti & Leite, 2013	new status
723. <i>Scinax proboscideus</i> (Brongersma, 1933)	
724. <i>Scinax ranki</i> (Andrade & Cardoso, 1987)	new status
725. <i>Scinax rizibilis</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	new status
726. <i>Scinax rogerioi</i> Pugliese, Baêta & Pombal, 2009	
727. <i>Scinax rossaferesae</i> Conte, Araujo-Vieira, Crivellari & Berneck, 2016	
728. <i>Scinax rostratus</i> (Peter, 1863)	
729. <i>Scinax ruber</i> (Laurenti, 1768)	
730. <i>Scinax ruberoculatus</i> Ferrão, Fraga, Moravec, Kaefer & Lima, 2018	
731. <i>Scinax rupestris</i> Araujo-Vieira, Brandão & Faria, 2015	
732. <i>Scinax sateremawe</i> Sturaro & Peloso, 2014	
733. <i>Scinax similis</i> (Cochran, 1952)	
734. <i>Scinax skaios</i> Pombal, Carvalho, Canelas & Bastos, 2010	new status
735. <i>Scinax skuki</i> Lima, Cruz & Azevedo, 2011	new status
736. <i>Scinax squalirostris</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
737. <i>Scinax strigilatus</i> (Spix, 1824)	new status

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
738. <i>Scinax strussmannae</i> Ferrão, Moravec, Kaefer, Fraga & Lima, 2018	
739. <i>Scinax tigrinus</i> Nunes, Carvalho & Pereira, 2010	
740. <i>Scinax trapicheiroi</i> (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1954)	new status
741. <i>Scinax tropicalia</i> Novaes-e-Fagundes, Araujo-Vieira, Entiauspe-Neto, Roberto, Orrico, Solé, Haddad & Loebmann, 2021	recently described species
742. <i>Scinax tymbamirim</i> Nunes, Kwet & Pombal, 2012	
743. <i>Scinax tripui</i> Lourenço, Nascimento & Pires, 2010	new status
744. <i>Scinax tupinamba</i> Silva & Alves-Silva, 2008	new status
745. <i>Scinax uruguayus</i> (Schmidt, 1944)	new status
746. <i>Scinax v-signatus</i> (B. Lutz, 1968)	new status
747. <i>Scinax villasboasi</i> Brusquetti, Jansen, Barrio-Amorós, Segalla & Haddad, 2014	
748. <i>Scinax x-signatus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
749. <i>Sphaenorhynchus botocudo</i> Caramaschi, Almeida & Gasparini, 2009	
750. <i>Sphaenorhynchus bromelicola</i> Bokermann, 1966	
751. <i>Sphaenorhynchus cammaeus</i> Roberto, Araujo-Vieira, S. Carvalho-e-Silva & Ávila, 2017	
752. <i>Sphaenorhynchus canga</i> Araujo-Vieira, Lacerda, Pezzuti, Leite, Assis & Cruz, 2015	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
753. <i>Sphaenorhynchus caramaschii</i> Toledo, Garcia, Lingnau & Haddad, 2007	
754. <i>Sphaenorhynchus carneus</i> (Cope, 1868)	
755. <i>Sphaenorhynchus dorisae</i> (Goin, 1957)	
756. <i>Sphaenorhynchus lacteus</i> (Daudin, 1800)	
757. <i>Sphaenorhynchus mirim</i> Caramaschi, Almeida & Gasparini, 2009	
758. <i>Sphaenorhynchus palustris</i> Bokermann, 1966	
759. <i>Sphaenorhynchus planicola</i> (A. Lutz & B. Lutz, 1938)	
760. <i>Sphaenorhynchus platycephalus</i> (Werner, 1894)	new status
761. <i>Sphaenorhynchus prasinus</i> Bokermann, 1973	
762. <i>Sphaenorhynchus surdus</i> (Cochran, 1953)	
Family Hylodidae	3 gen, 46 spp
763. <i>Crossodactylus boulengeri</i> (De Witte, 1930)	
764. <i>Crossodactylus caramaschii</i> Bastos & Pombal, 1995	
765. <i>Crossodactylus cyclopinus</i> Nascimento, Cruz & Feio, 2005	
766. <i>Crossodactylus dantei</i> Carcerelli & Caramaschi, 1993	
767. <i>Crossodactylus dispar</i> A. Lutz, 1925	
768. <i>Crossodactylus franciscanus</i> Pimenta, Caramaschi & Cruz, 2015	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
769. <i>Crossodactylus gaudichaudii</i> Duméril & Bibron, 1841	
770. <i>Crossodactylus grandis</i> B. Lutz, 1951	
771. <i>Crossodactylus lutzorum</i> Carcerelli & Caramaschi, 1993	
772. <i>Crossodactylus schmidti</i> Gallardo, 1961	
773. <i>Crossodactylus timbuhy</i> Pimenta, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2014	
774. <i>Crossodactylus trachystomus</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
775. <i>Crossodactylus weneri</i> Pimenta, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2014	
776. <i>Hylodes amnicola</i> Pombal, Feio & Haddad, 2002	
777. <i>Hylodes asper</i> (Müller, 1924)	
778. <i>Hylodes babax</i> Heyer, 1982	
779. <i>Hylodes caete</i> Malagoli, de Sá, Canedo & Haddad, 2017	
780. <i>Hylodes cardosoi</i> Lingnau, Canedo & Pombal, 2008	
781. <i>Hylodes charadranaetes</i> Heyer & Cocroft, 1986	
782. <i>Hylodes dactylocinus</i> Pavan, Narvaes & Rodrigues, 2001	
783. <i>Hylodes fredii</i> Canedo & Pombal, 2007	
784. <i>Hylodes glaber</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
785. <i>Hylodes heyeri</i> Haddad, Pombal & Bastos, 1996	
786. <i>Hylodes japi</i> de Sá, Canedo, Lyra & Haddad, 2015	
787. <i>Hylodes lateristrigatus</i> (Baumann, 1912)	
788. <i>Hylodes magalhaesi</i> (Bokermann, 1964)	
789. <i>Hylodes meridionalis</i> (Mertens, 1927)	
790. <i>Hylodes mertensi</i> (Bokermann, 1956)	
791. <i>Hylodes nasus</i> (Lichtenstein, 1823)	
792. <i>Hylodes ornatus</i> (Bokermann, 1967)	
793. <i>Hylodes otavioi</i> Sazima & Bokermann, 1983	
794. <i>Hylodes perere</i> Silva & Benmaman, 2008	
795. <i>Hylodes perplicatus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
796. <i>Hylodes phyllodes</i> Heyer & Cocroft, 1986	
797. <i>Hylodes pipilans</i> Canedo & Pombal, 2007	
798. <i>Hylodes regius</i> Gouvêa, 1979	
799. <i>Hylodes sazimai</i> Haddad & Pombal, 1995	
800. <i>Hylodes uai</i> Nascimento, Pombal & Haddad, 2001	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
801. <i>Hylodes vanzolinii</i> Heyer, 1982	
802. <i>Megaelosia apuana</i> Pombal, Prado & Canedo, 2003	
803. <i>Megaelosia bocainensis</i> Giaretta, Bokermann & Haddad, 1993	
804. <i>Megaelosia boticariana</i> Giaretta & Aguiar, 1998	
805. <i>Megaelosia goeldii</i> (Baumann, 1912)	
806. <i>Megaelosia jordanensis</i> (Heyer, 1983)	
807. <i>Megaelosia lutzae</i> Izecksohn & Gouvêa, 1987	
808. <i>Megaelosia massarti</i> (De Witte, 1930)	
Family Leptodactylidae (Leiuperinae)	5 gen, 75 spp
809. <i>Edalorhina perezii</i> Jiménez de la Espada, 1871	
810. <i>Engystomops freibergi</i> (Donoso-Barros, 1969)	
811. <i>Engystomops petersi</i> Jiménez de la Espada, 1872	
812. <i>Physalaemus aguirrei</i> Bokermann, 1966	
813. <i>Physalaemus albifrons</i> (Spix, 1824)	
814. <i>Physalaemus albonotatus</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
815. <i>Physalaemus angrensis</i> Weber, Gonzaga & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2005	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
816. <i>Physalaemus atim</i> Brasileiro & Haddad, 2015	
817. <i>Physalaemus atlanticus</i> Haddad & Sazima, 2004	
818. <i>Physalaemus barrioi</i> Bokermann, 1967	
819. <i>Physalaemus biligonigerus</i> (Cope, 1861)	
820. <i>Physalaemus bokermanni</i> Cardoso & Haddad, 1985	
821. <i>Physalaemus caete</i> Pombal & Madureira, 1997	
822. <i>Physalaemus camacan</i> Pimenta, Cruz & Silvano, 2005	
823. <i>Physalaemus carrizorum</i> Cardozo & Pereyra, 2018	
824. <i>Physalaemus centralis</i> Bokermann, 1962	
825. <i>Physalaemus cicada</i> Bokermann, 1966	
826. <i>Physalaemus claptoni</i> Leal, Leite, Costa, Nascimento, Lourenço & Garcia, 2020	recently described species
827. <i>Physalaemus crombiei</i> Heyer & Wolf, 1989	
828. <i>Physalaemus cuvieri</i> Fitzinger, 1826	
829. <i>Physalaemus deimaticus</i> Sazima & Caramaschi, 1988	
830. <i>Physalaemus ephippifer</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
831. <i>Physalaemus erikae</i> Cruz & Pimenta, 2004	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
832. <i>Physalaemus erythros</i> Caramaschi, Feio & Guimarães-Neto, 2003	
833. <i>Physalaemus evangelistai</i> Bokermann, 1967	
834. <i>Physalaemus feioi</i> Cassini, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2010	
835. <i>Physalaemus gracilis</i> (Boulenger, 1883)	
836. <i>Physalaemus henselii</i> (Peters, 1872)	
837. <i>Physalaemus insperatus</i> Cruz, Cassini & Caramaschi, 2008	
838. <i>Physalaemus irroratus</i> Cruz, Nascimento & Feio, 2007	
839. <i>Physalaemus jordanensis</i> Bokermann, 1967	
840. <i>Physalaemus kroyeri</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
841. <i>Physalaemus lateristriga</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
842. <i>Physalaemus lisei</i> P. Braun & C. Braun, 1977	
843. <i>Physalaemus maculiventris</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
844. <i>Physalaemus marmoratus</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
845. <i>Physalaemus maximus</i> Feio, Pombal & Caramaschi, 1999	
846. <i>Physalaemus moreirae</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
847. <i>Physalaemus nanus</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
848. <i>Physalaemus nattereri</i> (Steindachner, 1863)	
849. <i>Physalaemus obtectus</i> Bokermann, 1966	
850. <i>Physalaemus olfersii</i> (Lichtenstein & Martens, 1856)	
851. <i>Physalaemus orophilus</i> Cassini, Cruz & Caramaschi, 2010	
852. <i>Physalaemus riograndensis</i> Milstead, 1960	
853. <i>Physalaemus rupestris</i> Caramaschi, Carcerelli & Feio, 1991	
854. <i>Physalaemus signifer</i> (Girard, 1853)	
855. <i>Physalaemus soaresi</i> Izecksohn, 1965	
856. <i>Physalaemus spiniger</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
857. <i>Pleurodema alium</i> Maciel & Nunes, 2010	
858. <i>Pleurodema bibroni</i> Tschudi, 1838	
859. <i>Pleurodema brachyops</i> (Cope, 1869)	
860. <i>Pleurodema diplolister</i> (Peters, 1870)	
861. <i>Pseudopaludicola ameghini</i> (Cope, 1887)	
862. <i>Pseudopaludicola atragula</i> Pansonato, Mudrek, Veiga-Menocello, Rossa-Feres, Martins & Strüssmann, 2014	
863. <i>Pseudopaludicola boliviana</i> Parker, 1927	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
864. <i>Pseudopaludicola canga</i> Giaretta & Kokubum, 2003	
865. <i>Pseudopaludicola ceratophyes</i> Rivero & Serna, 1985	
866. <i>Pseudopaludicola coracolarinae</i> Andrade, Haga, Lyra, Carvalho, Haddad, Giaretta & Toledo, 2020b	recently described species
867. <i>Pseudopaludicola facureae</i> Andrade & Carvalho, 2013	
868. <i>Pseudopaludicola falcipes</i> (Hensel, 1867)	
869. <i>Pseudopaludicola florencei</i> Andrade, Haga, Lyra, Leite, Kwet, Haddad, Toledo & Giaretta, 2018	
870. <i>Pseudopaludicola giarettai</i> Carvalho, 2012	
871. <i>Pseudopaludicola hyleaustralis</i> Pansonato, Morais, Ávila, Kawashita-Ribeiro, Strüssmann & Martin, 2013	
872. <i>Pseudopaludicola ibisoroca</i> Pansonato, Veiga-Menoncello, Mudrek, Jansen, Recco-Pimentel, Martins & Strüssmann, 2016	
873. <i>Pseudopaludicola jaredi</i> Andrade, Magalhães, Nunes-de-Almeida, Veiga-Menoncello, Santana, Garda, Loebmann, Recco-Pimentel, Giaretta & Toledo, 2016	
874. <i>Pseudopaludicola jazmynmcdonaldae</i> Andrade, Silva, Koroiva, Fadel & Santana, 2019	
875. <i>Pseudopaludicola matuta</i> Andrade, Haga, Lyra, Carvalho, Haddad, Giaretta & Toledo, 2018	
876. <i>Pseudopaludicola mineira</i> Lobo, 1994	
877. <i>Pseudopaludicola motorzinho</i> Pansonato, Veiga-Menoncello, Mudrek, Jansen, Recco-Pimentel, Martins & Strüssmann, 2016	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
878. <i>Pseudopaludicola murundu</i> Toledo, Siqueira, Duarte, Veiga-Menoncello, Recco-Pimentel & Haddad, 2010	
879. <i>Pseudopaludicola mystacalis</i> (Cope, 1887)	
880. <i>Pseudopaludicola pocoto</i> Magalhães, Loebmann, Kokubum, Haddad & Garda, 2014	
881. <i>Pseudopaludicola restinga</i> Cardozo, Baldo, Pupin, Gasparini, & Haddad, 2018	
882. <i>Pseudopaludicola saltica</i> (Cope, 1887)	
883. <i>Pseudopaludicola ternetzi</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937	
Family Leptodactylidae (Leptodactylinae)	4 gen, 92 spp
884. <i>Adenomera ajurauna</i> (Berneck, Costa & Garcia 2008)	
885. <i>Adenomera amicorum</i> Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2020	recently described species
886. <i>Adenomera andreae</i> (Müller, 1923)	
887. <i>Adenomera araucaria</i> Kwet & Angulo, 2003	
888. <i>Adenomera aurantiaca</i> Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2020	recently described species
889. <i>Adenomera bokermanni</i> (Heyer, 1973)	
890. <i>Adenomera chicomendesi</i> Carvalho, Angulo, Kokubum, Barrera, Souza, Haddad & Giaretta, 2019	recently described species
891. <i>Adenomera cotuba</i> Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013	
892. <i>Adenomera diptyx</i> (Boettger, 1885)	
893. <i>Adenomera engelsi</i> Kwet, Steiner & Zillikens, 2009	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
894. <i>Adenomera glauciae</i> Carvalho, Simões, Gagliardi-Urrutia, Rojas-Runjaic, Haddad & Castroviejo-Fisher, 2020	recently described species
895. <i>Adenomera gridipappi</i> Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira, & Haddad, 2021	recently described species
896. <i>Adenomera heyeri</i> Boistel, Massary & Angulo, 2006	
897. <i>Adenomera hylaedactyla</i> (Cope, 1868)	
898. <i>Adenomera inopinata</i> Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021	recently described species
899. <i>Adenomera juikitam</i> Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013	
900. <i>Adenomera kayapo</i> Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021	recently described species
901. <i>Adenomera kweti</i> Carvalho, Cassini, Taucce & Haddad, 2019	recently described species
902. <i>Adenomera marmorata</i> (Steindachner, 1867)	
903. <i>Adenomera martinezi</i> (Bokermann, 1956)	
904. <i>Adenomera nana</i> (Müller, 1922)	
905. <i>Adenomera phonotriccus</i> Carvalho, Giaretta, Angulo, Haddad & Peloso, 2019	
906. <i>Adenomera saci</i> Carvalho & Giaretta, 2013	
907. <i>Adenomera simonstuarti</i> (Angulo & Icochea, 2010)	new occurrence (Carvalho et al., 2020b)
908. <i>Adenomera tapajonica</i> Carvalho, Moraes, Lima, Fouquet, Peloso, Pavan, Drummond, Rodrigues, Giaretta, Gordo, Neckel-Oliveira & Haddad, 2021	recently described species

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
909. <i>Adenomera thomei</i> (Almeida & Angulo, 2006)	
910. <i>Hydrolaetare caparu</i> Jansen, Gonzalez-Álvares & Köhler, 2007	
911. <i>Hydrolaetare dantasi</i> (Bokermann, 1959)	
912. <i>Hydrolaetare schmidtii</i> (Cochran & Goin, 1959)	
913. <i>Leptodactylus barrioi</i> Silva, Magalhães, Thomassen, Leite, Garda, Brandão, Haddad, Giaretta & Carvalho, 2020	recently described species
914. <i>Leptodactylus bolivianus</i> Boulenger, 1898	
915. <i>Leptodactylus brevipes</i> Cope, 1887	recently revalited species (Gazoni et al., 2021)
916. <i>Leptodactylus bufonius</i> Boulenger, 1894	
917. <i>Leptodactylus caatingae</i> Heyer & Juncá, 2003	
918. <i>Leptodactylus camaquara</i> Sazima & Bokermann, 1978	
919. <i>Leptodactylus cunicularius</i> Sazima & Bokermann, 1978	
920. <i>Leptodactylus cupreus</i> Caramaschi, Feio & São-Pedro, 2008	
921. <i>Leptodactylus didymus</i> Heyer, García-Lopez & Cardoso, 1996	
922. <i>Leptodactylus diedrus</i> Heyer, 1994	
923. <i>Leptodactylus discodactylus</i> Boulenger, 1884	
924. <i>Leptodactylus elenae</i> Heyer, 1978	
925. <i>Leptodactylus flavopictus</i> A. Lutz, 1926	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
926. <i>Leptodactylus furnarius</i> Sazima & Bokermann, 1978	
927. <i>Leptodactylus fuscus</i> (Schneider, 1799)	
928. <i>Leptodactylus gracilis</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	
929. <i>Leptodactylus guianensis</i> Heyer & de Sá, 2011	
930. <i>Leptodactylus hylodes</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
931. <i>Leptodactylus intermedius</i> A. Lutz, 1930	recently revalited species (Gazoni et al., 2021)
932. <i>Leptodactylus jolyi</i> Sazima & Bokermann, 1978	
933. <i>Leptodactylus kilombo</i> Silva, Magalhães, Thomassen, Leite, Garda, Brandão, Haddad, Giaretta & Carvalho, 2020	recently described species
934. <i>Leptodactylus knudseni</i> Heyer, 1972	
935. <i>Leptodactylus labyrinthicus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
936. <i>Leptodactylus latinasus</i> Jiménez de la Espada, 1875	
937. <i>Leptodactylus latrans</i> (Steffen, 1815)	
938. <i>Leptodactylus lauramiriamae</i> Heyer & Crombie, 2005	
939. <i>Leptodactylus leptodactyloides</i> (Andersson, 1945)	
940. <i>Leptodactylus longirostris</i> Boulenger, 1882	
941. <i>Leptodactylus luctator</i> (Hudson, 1892)	recently revalidated species (Magalhães et al., 2020a)
942. <i>Leptodactylus macrosternum</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
943. <i>Leptodactylus marambaiae</i> Izecksohn, 1976	
944. <i>Leptodactylus myersi</i> Heyer, 1995	
945. <i>Leptodactylus mystaceus</i> (Spix, 1824)	
946. <i>Leptodactylus mystacinus</i> (Burmeister, 1861)	
947. <i>Leptodactylus natalensis</i> A. Lutz, 1930	
948. <i>Leptodactylus notoaktites</i> Heyer, 1978	
949. <i>Leptodactylus ochraceus</i> A. Lutz, 1930	
950. <i>Leptodactylus oreomantis</i> Carvalho, Leite & Pezzuti, 2013	
951. <i>Leptodactylus paraensis</i> Heyer, 2005	
952. <i>Leptodactylus paranaru</i> Magalhães, Lyra, Carvalho, Baldo, Brusquetti, Burella, Colli, Gehara, Giaretta, Haddad, Langone, López, Napoli, Santana, de Sá & Garda, 2020	recently described species
953. <i>Leptodactylus payaya</i> Magalhães, Lyra, Carvalho, Baldo, Brusquetti, Burella, Colli, Gehara, Giaretta, Haddad, Langone, López, Napoli, Santana, de Sá & Garda, 2020	recently described species
954. <i>Leptodactylus pentadactylus</i> (Laurenti, 1768)	
955. <i>Leptodactylus petersii</i> (Steindachner, 1864)	
956. <i>Leptodactylus plaumanni</i> Ahl, 1936	
957. <i>Leptodactylus podicipinus</i> (Cope, 1862)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
958. <i>Leptodactylus pustulatus</i> (Peters, 1870)	
959. <i>Leptodactylus rhodomystax</i> Boulenger, 1884	
960. <i>Leptodactylus rhodonotus</i> (Günther, 1869)	
961. <i>Leptodactylus riveroi</i> Heyer & Pyburn, 1983	
962. <i>Leptodactylus rugosus</i> Noble, 1923	
963. <i>Leptodactylus sabanensis</i> Heyer, 1994	
964. <i>Leptodactylus sertanejo</i> Giaretta & Costa, 2007	
965. <i>Leptodactylus spixi</i> Heyer, 1983	
966. <i>Leptodactylus stenodema</i> Jiménez de la Espada, 1875	
967. <i>Leptodactylus siphax</i> Bokermann, 1969	
968. <i>Leptodactylus tapiti</i> Sazima & Bokermann, 1978	
969. <i>Leptodactylus troglodytes</i> A. Lutz, 1926	
970. <i>Leptodactylus validus</i> Garman, 1888	
971. <i>Leptodactylus vastus</i> A. Lutz, 1930	
972. <i>Leptodactylus viridis</i> Jim & Spirandeli-Cruz, 1973	
973. <i>Leptodactylus wagneri</i> (Peters, 1862)	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
974. <i>Leptodactylus wutu</i> Silva, Magalhães, Thomassen, Leite, Garda, Brandão, Haddad, Giaretta & Carvalho, 2020	recently described species
975. <i>Lithodytes lineatus</i> (Schneider, 1799)	
Family Leptodactylidae (Paratelmatobiinae)	4 gen, 14 spp
976. <i>Crossodactylodes bokermanni</i> Peixoto, 1983	
977. <i>Crossodactylodes itambe</i> Barata, Santos, Leite & Garcia, 2013	
978. <i>Crossodactylodes izecksohni</i> Peixoto, 1983	
979. <i>Crossodactylodes pinto</i> Cochran, 1938	
980. <i>Crossodactylodes septentrionalis</i> Teixeira, Recoder, Amaro, Damasceno, Cassimiro & Rodrigues, 2013	
981. <i>Paratelmatobius cardosoi</i> Pombal & Haddad, 1999	
982. <i>Paratelmatobius gaigeae</i> (Cochran, 1938)	
983. <i>Paratelmatobius lutzii</i> B. Lutz & Carvalho, 1958	
984. <i>Paratelmatobius mantiqueira</i> Pombal & Haddad, 1999	
985. <i>Paratelmatobius poecilogaster</i> Giaretta & Castanho, 1990	
986. <i>Paratelmatobius segallai</i> Santos, Oliveira, Carvalho, Zaidan, Silva, Berneck & Garcia, 2019	recently described species
987. <i>Paratelmatobius yepiranga</i> Garcia, Berneck & Costa, 2009	
988. <i>Rupirana cardosoi</i> Heyer, 1999	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
989. <i>Scythrophrys sawayae</i> (Cochran, 1953)	
Family Microhylidae (Adelastinae)	1 gen, 1 sp
990. <i>Adelastes hylonomus</i> Zweifel, 1986	
Family Microhylidae (Gastrophryninae)	10 gen, 55 spp
991. <i>Arcovomer passarellii</i> Carvalho, 1954	
992. <i>Chiasmocleis alagoana</i> Cruz, Caramaschi & Freire, 1999	
993. <i>Chiasmocleis albopunctata</i> (Boettger, 1885)	
994. <i>Chiasmocleis altomontana</i> Forlani, Tonini, Cruz, Zaher & de Sá, 2017	
995. <i>Chiasmocleis antenori</i> (Walker, 1973)	
996. <i>Chiasmocleis atlantica</i> Cruz, Caramaschi & Izecksohn, 1997	
997. <i>Chiasmocleis avilapiresae</i> Peloso & Sturaro 2008	
998. <i>Chiasmocleis bassleri</i> Dunn, 1949	
999. <i>Chiasmocleis bicegoi</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920	
1000. <i>Chiasmocleis capixaba</i> Cruz, Caramaschi & Izecksohn, 1997	
1001. <i>Chiasmocleis centralis</i> Bokermann, 1952	
1002. <i>Chiasmocleis cordeiroi</i> Caramaschi & Pimenta, 2003	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1003. <i>Chiasmocleis crucis</i> Caramaschi & Pimenta, 2003	
1004. <i>Chiasmocleis haddadi</i> Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014	
1005. <i>Chiasmocleis hudsoni</i> Parker, 1940	
1006. <i>Chiasmocleis jimi</i> Caramaschi & Cruz, 2001	
1007. <i>Chiasmocleis lacrimae</i> Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014	
1008. <i>Chiasmocleis leucosticta</i> (Boulenger, 1888)	
1009. <i>Chiasmocleis mantiqueira</i> Cruz, Feio & Cassini, 2007	
1010. <i>Chiasmocleis mehelyi</i> Caramaschi & Cruz, 1997	
1011. <i>Chiasmocleis migueli</i> Forlani, Tonini, Cruz, Zaher & de Sá, 2017	
1012. <i>Chiasmocleis papachibe</i> Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014	
1013. <i>Chiasmocleis quilombola</i> Tonini, Forlani & de Sá, 2014	
1014. <i>Chiasmocleis royi</i> Peloso, Sturaro, Forlani, Gaucher, Motta & Wheeler, 2014	
1015. <i>Chiasmocleis sapiranga</i> Cruz, Caramaschi & Napoli, 2007	
1016. <i>Chiasmocleis schubarti</i> Bokermann, 1952	
1017. <i>Chiasmocleis shudikarensis</i> Dunn, 1949	
1018. <i>Chiasmocleis superciliarba</i> Morales & McDiarmid, 2009	new occurrence (França et al., 2013)

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1019. <i>Chiasmocleis tridactyla</i> (Duellman & Medelson, 1995)	
1020. <i>Chiasmocleis ventrimaculata</i> (Andersson, 1945)	
1021. <i>Chiasmocleis veracruz</i> Forlani, Tonini, Cruz, Zaher & de Sá, 2017	
1022. <i>Ctenophryne geayi</i> Mocquard, 1904	
1023. <i>Dasylops schirchi</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1924	
1024. <i>Dermatonotus muelleri</i> (Boettger, 1885)	
1025. <i>Elachistocleis bicolor</i> (Valenciennes in Guérin-Ménéville, 1838)	
1026. <i>Elachistocleis bumbameuboi</i> Caramaschi, 2010	
1027. <i>Elachistocleis carvalhoi</i> Caramaschi, 2010	
1028. <i>Elachistocleis cesarii</i> (Miranda Ribeiro, 1920)	
1029. <i>Elachistocleis corumbaensis</i> Piva, Caramaschi & Albuquerque, 2017	
1030. <i>Elachistocleis erythrogaster</i> Kwet & Di-Bernardo, 1998	
1031. <i>Elachistocleis helianneae</i> Caramaschi, 2010	
1032. <i>Elachistocleis magna</i> Toledo, 2010	
10343 <i>Elachistocleis matogrosso</i> Caramaschi, 2010	
1034. <i>Elachistocleis muiraquitana</i> Nunes-de-Almeida & Toledo, 2012	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1035. <i>Elachistocleis piauiensis</i> Caramaschi & Jim, 1983	
1036. <i>Elachistocleis surinamensis</i> (Daudin, 1802)	new record (Jowers et al., 2021)
1037. <i>Elachistocleis surumu</i> Caramaschi, 2010	
1038. <i>Hamptophryne alios</i> (Wild, 1995)	
1039. <i>Hamptophryne boliviana</i> (Parker, 1927)	
1040. <i>Myersiella microps</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	
1041. <i>Relictocleis gnoma</i> (Canedo, Dixo & Pombal, 2004)	recently described genus (Dubois et al., 2021)
1042. <i>Stereocyclops histrio</i> (Carvalho, 1954)	
1043. <i>Stereocyclops incrassatus</i> Cope, 1870	
1044. <i>Stereocyclops palmipes</i> Caramaschi, Salles & Cruz, 2012	
1045. <i>Stereocyclops parkeri</i> (Wettstein, 1934)	
Family Microhylidae (Otophryninae)	2 gen, 3 spp
1046. <i>Otophryne pyburni</i> Campbell & Clarke, 1998	
1047. <i>Synapturanus mirandaribeiroi</i> Nelson & Lescure, 1975	
1048. <i>Synapturanus salseri</i> Pyburn, 1975	
Family Odontophrynidae	3 gen, 48 spp
1049. <i>Macrogenioglottus alipioi</i> Carvalho, 1946	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1050. <i>Odontophrynus americanus</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	
1051. <i>Odontophrynus carvalhoi</i> Savage & Cei, 1965	
1052. <i>Odontophrynus cultripes</i> Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862	
1053. <i>Odontophrynus juquinha</i> Rocha, Sena, Pezzuti, Leite, Svartman, Rosset, Baldo & Garcia, 2017	
1054. <i>Odontophrynus lavillai</i> Cei, 1985	
1055. <i>Odontophrynus maisuma</i> Rosset, 2008	
1056. <i>Odontophrynus monachus</i> Caramaschi & Napoli, 2012	
1057. <i>Proceratophrys appendiculata</i> (Günther, 1873)	
1058. <i>Proceratophrys ararype</i> Mângia, Koroiva, Nunes, Roberto, Ávila, Sant'Anna, Santana & Garda, 2018	
1059. <i>Proceratophrys avelinoi</i> Mercadal de Barrio & Barrio, 1993	
1060. <i>Proceratophrys bagnoi</i> Brandão, Caramaschi, Vaz-Silva & Campos, 2013	
1061. <i>Proceratophrys belzebul</i> Dias, Amaro, A. Carvalho-e-Silva & Rodrigues, 2013	
1062. <i>Proceratophrys bigibbosa</i> (Peters, 1872)	
1063. <i>Proceratophrys boiei</i> (Wied-Neuwied, 1824)	
1064. <i>Proceratophrys branti</i> Brandão, Caramaschi, Vaz-Silva & Campos, 2013	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1065. <i>Proceratophrys brauni</i> Kwet & Faivovich, 2001	
1066. <i>Proceratophrys carranca</i> Godinho, Moura, Lacerda & Feio, 2013	
1067. <i>Proceratophrys concavitympanum</i> Giaretta, Bernarde & Kokubum, 2000	
1068. <i>Proceratophrys cristiceps</i> (Müller, 1883)	
1069. <i>Proceratophrys cururu</i> Eterovick & Sazima, 1998	
1070. <i>Proceratophrys dibernardoi</i> Brandão, Caramaschi, Vaz-Silva & Campos, 2013	
1071. <i>Proceratophrys gladius</i> Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014	
1072. <i>Proceratophrys goyana</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
1073. <i>Proceratophrys huntingtoni</i> Avila, Pansonato & Strüssmann, 2012	
1074. <i>Proceratophrys itamari</i> Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014	
1075. <i>Proceratophrys izecksohni</i> Dias, Amaro, A. Carvalho-e-Silva & Rodrigues, 2013	
1076. <i>Proceratophrys laticeps</i> Izecksohn & Peixoto, 1981	
1077. <i>Proceratophrys mantiqueira</i> Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014	
1078. <i>Proceratophrys melanopogon</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
1079. <i>Proceratophrys minuta</i> Napoli, Cruz, Abreu & Del-Grande, 2011	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1080. <i>Proceratophrys moehringi</i> Weygoldt & Peixoto, 1985	
1081. <i>Proceratophrys moratoi</i> (Jim & Caramaschi, 1980)	
1082. <i>Proceratophrys palustris</i> Giaretta & Sazima, 1993	
1083. <i>Proceratophrys paviotii</i> Cruz, Prado & Izecksohn, 2005	
1084. <i>Proceratophrys phyllostomus</i> Izecksohn, Cruz & Peixoto, 1999	
1085. <i>Proceratophrys pombali</i> Mângia, Santana, Cruz & Feio, 2014	
1086. <i>Proceratophrys redacta</i> Teixeira, Amaro, Recoder, Vechio & Rodrigues, 2012	
1087. <i>Proceratophrys renalis</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920)	
1088. <i>Proceratophrys rondonae</i> Prado & Pombal, 2008	
1089. <i>Proceratophrys rotundipalpebra</i> Martins & Giaretta, 2013	
1090. <i>Proceratophrys salvatori</i> (Caramaschi, 1996)	new status (Magalhães et al., 2020b)
1091. <i>Proceratophrys sanctaritae</i> Cruz & Napoli, 2010	
1092. <i>Proceratophrys schirchi</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
1093. <i>Proceratophrys strussmannae</i> Ávila, Kawashita-Ribeiro & Morais, 2011	
1094. <i>Proceratophrys subguttata</i> Izecksohn, Cruz & Peixoto, 1999	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1095. <i>Proceratophrys tupinamba</i> Prado & Pombal, 2008	
1096. <i>Proceratophrys vielliardi</i> Martins & Giaretta, 2011	
Family Phyllomedusidae	7 gen, 42 spp
1097. <i>Callimedusa atelopoides</i> (Duellman, Cadle & Cannatella, 1988)	
1098. <i>Callimedusa tomopterna</i> (Cope, 1868)	
1099. <i>Cruziophyla craspedopus</i> (Funkhouser, 1957)	
1100. <i>Hylomantis aspera</i> (Peters, 1873)	
1101. <i>Hylomantis granulosa</i> (Cruz, 1989)	
1102. <i>Phasmahyla cochranæ</i> (Bokermann, 1966)	
1103. <i>Phasmahyla cruzi</i> A. Carvalho-e-Silva, Silva & S. Carvalho-e-Silva, 2009	
1104. <i>Phasmahyla exilis</i> (Cruz, 1980)	
1105. <i>Phasmahyla guttata</i> (A. Lutz, 1924)	
1106. <i>Phasmahyla jandaia</i> (Bokermann & Sazima, 1978)	
1107. <i>Phasmahyla lisbella</i> Pereira, Rocha, Folly, Silva & Santana, 2018	
1108. <i>Phasmahyla spectabilis</i> Cruz, Feio & Nascimento, 2008	
1109. <i>Phasmahyla timbo</i> Cruz, Napoli & Fonseca, 2008	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1110. <i>Phrynomedusa appendiculata</i> (A. Lutz, 1925)	
1111. <i>Phrynomedusa bokermanni</i> Cruz, 1991	
1112. <i>Phrynomedusa dryade</i> Baêta, Giasson, Pombal & Haddad, 2016	
1113. <i>Phrynomedusa fimbriata</i> Miranda-Ribeiro, 1923	
1114. <i>Phrynomedusa marginata</i> (Izecksohn & Cruz, 1976)	
1115. <i>Phrynomedusa vanzolinii</i> Cruz, 1991	
1116. <i>Phyllomedusa bahiana</i> A. Lutz, 1925	
1117. <i>Phyllomedusa bicolor</i> (Boddaert, 1772)	
1118. <i>Phyllomedusa boliviana</i> Boulenger, 1902	
1119. <i>Phyllomedusa burmeisteri</i> Boulenger, 1882	
1120. <i>Phyllomedusa camba</i> De la Riva, 2000	
1121. <i>Phyllomedusa distincta</i> A. Lutz in B. Lutz, 1950	
1122. <i>Phyllomedusa iheringii</i> Boulenger, 1885	
1123. <i>Phyllomedusa sauvagii</i> Boulenger, 1882	
1124. <i>Phyllomedusa tarsius</i> (Cope, 1868)	
1125. <i>Phyllomedusa tetraploidea</i> Pombal & Haddad, 1992	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1126. <i>Phyllomedusa vaillantii</i> Boulenger, 1882	
1127. <i>Pithecopus araguaianus</i> Haga, Andrade, Bruschi, Recco-Pimentel & Giaretta, 2017	
1128. <i>Pithecopus ayeaye</i> B. Lutz, 1966	
1129. <i>Pithecopus azureus</i> (Cope, 1862)	
1130. <i>Pithecopus centralis</i> (Bokermann, 1965)	
1131. <i>Pithecopus gonzagai</i> Andrade, Haga, Ferreira, Recco-Pimentel, Toledo & Bruschi, 2020a	recently described species
1132. <i>Pithecopus hypochondrialis</i> (Daudin, 1800)	
1133. <i>Pithecopus megacephalus</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926)	
1134. <i>Pithecopus nordestinus</i> (Caramaschi, 2006)	
1135. <i>Pithecopus oreades</i> (Brandão, 2002)	
1136. <i>Pithecopus palliatus</i> (Peters, 1873)	
1137. <i>Pithecopus rohdei</i> (Mertens, 1926)	
1138. <i>Pithecopus rusticus</i> (Bruschi, Lucas, Garcia & Recco-Pimentel, 2016)	
Family Pipidae	1 gen, 4 spp
1139. <i>Pipa arrabali</i> Izecksohn, 1976	

ORDER ANURA	STATUS
1140. <i>Pipa carvalhoi</i> (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1937)	
1141. <i>Pipa pipa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	
1142. <i>Pipa snethlageae</i> Müller, 1914	
Family Ranidae	2 gen, 2 spp
1143. <i>Aquarana catesbeiana</i> (Shaw, 1802)	new status and invasive species
1144. <i>Lithobates palmipes</i> (Spix, 1824)	
ORDER CAUDATA	STATUS
Family Plethodontidae (Plethodontinae)	1 gen, 5 spp
1145. <i>Bolitoglossa altamazonica</i> (Cope, 1874)	
1146. <i>Bolitoglossa caldwella</i> Brcko, Hoogmoed & Neckel-Oliveira, 2013	
1147. <i>Bolitoglossa madeira</i> Brcko, Hoogmoed & Neckel-Oliveira, 2013	
1148. <i>Bolitoglossa paraensis</i> (Unterstein, 1930)	
1149. <i>Bolitoglossa tapajonica</i> Brcko, Hoogmoed & Neckel-Oliveira, 2013	
ORDER GYMNOPTIONA	STATUS
Family Caeciliidae	2 gen, 5 spp
1150. <i>Caecilia armata</i> Dunn, 1942	

ORDER GYMNOPIHIONA	STATUS
1151. <i>Caecilia gracilis</i> Shaw, 1802	
1152. <i>Caecilia marcusii</i> Wake, 1985	improved identification
1153. <i>Caecilia tentaculata</i> Linnaeus, 1758	
1154. <i>Osaecilia hypereumeces</i> Taylor, 1968	
Family Rhinatrematidae	1 gen, 4 spp
1155. <i>Rhinatrema bivittatum</i> (Guérin-Méneville, 1838)	
1156. <i>Rhinatrema gilbertogili</i> Maciel, Sampaio, Hoogmoed & Schneider, 2018	
1157. <i>Rhinatrema ron</i> Wilkinson & Gower, 2010	
1158. <i>Rhinatrema uaiuai</i> Maciel, Sampaio, Hoogmoed & Schneider, 2018	
Family Siphonopidae	5 gen, 18 spp
1159. <i>Brasilotyphlus braziliensis</i> (Dunn, 1945)	
1160. <i>Brasilotyphlus dubium</i> Correia, Nunes, Gamble, Maciel, Marques-Souza, Fouquet, Rodrigues & Mott, 2018	
1161. <i>Brasilotyphlus guarantanus</i> Maciel, Mott & Hoogmoed, 2009	
1162. <i>Luetkenotyphlus brasiliensis</i> (Lütken, 1852)	
1163. <i>Luetkenotyphlus fredii</i> Maciel, Castro, Sturaro, Silva, Ferreira, Santos, Risse-Quaioto, Barboza, Oliveira, Sampaio & Schneider, 2019	recently described species

ORDER GYMNOPIHIONA	STATUS
1164. <i>Luetkenotyphlus insulanus</i> (Ihering, 1911)	new status (Maciel et al. 2019)
1165. <i>Microcaecilia butantan</i> Wilkinson, Antoniazzi & Jared, 2015	
1166. <i>Microcaecilia marvaleewakeae</i> Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2013	
1167. <i>Microcaecilia rochai</i> Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011	
1168. <i>Microcaecilia supernumeraria</i> Taylor, 1969	
1169. <i>Microcaecilia taylori</i> Nussbaum & Hoogmoed, 1979	
1170. <i>Microcaecilia trombetas</i> Maciel & Hoogmoed, 2011	
1171. <i>Mimosiphonops reinhardti</i> Wilkinson & Nussbaum, 1992	
1172. <i>Mimosiphonops vermiculatus</i> Taylor, 1968	
1173. <i>Siphonops annulatus</i> (Mikan, 1820)	
1174. <i>Siphonops hardyi</i> Boulenger, 1888	
1175. <i>Siphonops leucoderus</i> Taylor, 1968	
1176. <i>Siphonops paulensis</i> Boettger, 1892	
Family Typhlonectidae	5 gen, 12 spp
1177. <i>Atretochoana eiselti</i> (Taylor, 1968)	
1178. <i>Chthonerpeton arii</i> Cascon & Lima-Verde, 1994	

ORDER GYMNOPIHONA	STATUS
1179. <i>Chthonerpeton braestrupi</i> Taylor, 1968	
1180. <i>Chthonerpeton exile</i> Nussbaum & Wilkinson, 1987	
1181. <i>Chthonerpeton indistinctum</i> (Reinhardt & Lütken, 1862)	
1182. <i>Chthonerpeton noctinectes</i> da Silva, Britto-Pereira & Caramaschi, 2003	
1183. <i>Chthonerpeton perissodus</i> Nussbaum & Wilkinson 1987	
1184. <i>Chthonerpeton tremembe</i> Maciel, Leite, Silva-Leite, Leite & Cascon, 2015	
1185. <i>Chthonerpeton viviparum</i> Parker & Wettstein, 1929	
1186. <i>Nectocaecilia petersii</i> (Boulenger, 1882)	
1187. <i>Potomotyphlus kaupii</i> (Berthold, 1859)	
1188. <i>Typhlonectes compressicauda</i> (Duméril & Bibron, 1841)	

Acknowledgments:

We are grateful to Dione Seripierri granting emergency access to the MZUSP library during the COVID-19 pandemic.

References

- Alves da Silva, L., C. S. Carvalho, E. A. Pereira Silva, R. M. Fadel, S. P. Dantas, R. A. Brandão, and D. J. Santana. 2020. Richness, diversity patterns, and taxonomic notes of amphibians from the Tocantins state. *Biota Neotropica* 20 (1: e20190838):1–22. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1676-0611-bn-2019-0838>
- Andrade F.S., Haga I.A., Lyra M.L., Carvalho T.R., Haddad C.F.B., Giaretta, A.A., Toledo L.F. 2020a. Reassessment of the taxonomic status of *Pseudopaludicola parnaíba* (Anura, Leptodactylidae, Leiuperinae), with the description of a new cryptic species from the Brazilian Cerrado. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 679:1–36. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2020.679>.
- Andrade F.S., Haga I.A., Ferreira J.S., Recco-Pimentel S.M., Toledo L.F., Bruschi, D.P. 2020b. A new cryptic species of *Pithecopus* (Anura, Phyllomedusidae) in north-eastern Brazil. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 723:108–134. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2020.723.1147>.
- Araujo-Vieira K., Caramaschi U., Grillitsch H., Grant T., Faivovich J. 2018. On the identity of *Sphaenorhynchus platycephalus* (Werner, 1894) (Anura: Hylidae). *South American Journal of Herpetology* 13:73–84. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2994/SAJH-D-17-00053.1>.
- Araujo-Vieira A., Luna M.C., Caramaschi U., Haddad C.F.B. 2020. A new genus of lime tree-frogs (Anura: Hylidae: Sphaenorhynchini). *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 286:81–89. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2020.04.002>.
- Araujo-Vieira K., Pombal Jr. J.P., Caramaschi U., Novaes-e-Fagundes G, Orrico V.G.D., Faivovich J. 2020. A neotype for *Hyla x-signata* Spix, 1824 (Amphibia, Anura, Hylidae). *Papéis Avulsos de Zoologia* 6:1–30. doi: <http://doi.org/10.11606/1807-0205/2020.60.56>.
- Ávila R.W., Morais D.H., Perez R., Pansonato A., Carvalho V.T., Rojas-Zamora R.R., Gordo, M., Farias I.P. 2020. A new species of the *Rhinella margaritifera* (Laurenti 1768) species group (Anura, Bufonidae) from southern Brazilian Amazonia. *Zootaxa* 4868:368–388. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4868.3.3>.
- Baldo D., Araujo-Vieira K., Cardozo D., Borteiro C., Leal F., Pereyra M.O., ..., Faivovich J. 2019. A review of the elusive bicolored iris Snouted Treefrogs (Anura: Hylidae: *Scinax uruguayus* group). *PLoS One* 14:e0222131. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0222131>.

Blotto B., Lyra M.L., Cardoso M.C.S., Rodrigues M.T., Dias I.R., Marciano-Jr. E., ..., Faivovich J. 2021. The phylogeny of the Casque-headed Treefrogs (Hylidae: Hylinae: Lophohylini). *Cladistics* 37:36–72. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/cla.12409>.

Caminer M.A., Ron S.R. 2014. Systematics of treefrogs of the *Hypsiboas calcaratus* and *Hypsiboas fasciatus* species complex (Anura, Hylidae) with the description of four new species. *ZooKeys* 370:1–68.

Caminer M.A., Ron S.R. 2020. Systematics of the *Boana semilineata* species group (Anura: Hylidae), with a description of two new species from Amazonian Ecuador. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 190:149–180. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnea/zlaa002>.

Carvalho T.R., Cassini C.S., Taucce P.P.G., Haddad C.F.B. 2019. A new, morphologically cryptic species of *Adenomera* closely related to *Adenomera araucaria* from the Atlantic Forest of Southern Brazil (Anura, Leptodactylidae). *Journal of Herpetology* 53:131–143. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1670/18-172>.

Carvalho T.R., Angulo A., Kokubum M.N.C., Barrera, D.A., Souza M.B., ..., Giaretta, A.A. 2019. A new cryptic species of the *Adenomera andreae* clade from southwestern Amazonia (Anura, Leptodactylidae). *Herpetologica* 75:233–246. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1655/D-18-00049>.

Carvalho T.R., Simões P.I., Gagliardi-Urrutia L.A.G., Rojas-Runjaic F.J.M., Haddad C.F.B. Castroviejo-Fisher, S. 2020a. A new forest-dwelling frog species of the genus *Adenomera* (Leptodactylidae) from northwestern Brazilian Amazonia. *Copeia* 108: 924–937. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1643/CH-19-329>.

Carvalho T.R., Moraes L.J.C.L., Angulo A., Werneck F.P., Icochea J., Lima, A.P. 2020b. New acoustic and molecular data shed light on the poorly known Amazonian frog *Adenomera simon-stuarti* (Leptodactylidae): implications for distribution and conservation. *European Journal of Taxonomy* 682:1–18. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5852/ejt.2020.682>

Carvalho T.R., Moraes L.J.C.L., Lima A.P., Fouquet A., Peloso P.L.V., Pavan D., ..., Haddad C.F.B. 2021. Systematics and historical biogeography of Neotropical foam-nesting frogs of the *Adenomera heyeri* clade (Leptodactylidae), with the description of six new Amazonian species. *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society* 191:395–433. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnea/zlaa051>.

- Castroviejo-Fisher S., Padial J.M., De la Riva I., Pombal Jr. J.P., Silva H.R., Rojas-Runjaic, F. J.M., ..., Frost, D.R. 2015. Phylogenetic systematics of egg-brooding frogs (Anura: Hemiphraclidae) and the evolution of direct development. *Zootaxa* 4004:1–75. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4004.1.1>.
- Colaço G., Silva H.R. 2016. On the type series of *Scinax perpusillus* (Lutz & Lutz, 1939) (Anura: Hylidae). *Zootaxa*, 4154:193–196. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4154.2.7>.
- Costa-Campos C.E., Barbosa-Figueiredo V.A.M., Jairam R., Fouquet, A. 2020a. Distribution extension of *Rhinella lescurei* (Bufonidae) in the state of Amapá, Brazil. *Herpetological Notes* 13:801–804.
- Costa-Campos C.E., Pinheiro R.T., Castroviejo-Fisher S. 2020b. Amphibia, Anura, Centrolenidae, *Cochranella resplendens* (Lynch & Duellman, 1973): first record from Brazil and updated map of the geographic distribution. *Check List* 16:847. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15560/16.4.847>.
- Costa-Campos C.E., Bang D.L., Figueiredo V.A.B., Tavares-Pinheiro R., Fouquet A. 2021. New records and distribution extensions of the glassfrogs *Hyalinobatrachium taylori* (Goin, 1968) and *H. tricolor* Castroviejo-Fisher, Vilà, Ayarzagüena, Blanc & Ernst, 2011 (Anura, Centrolenidae) in Amapá, Brazil. *Check List* 17:637-642. <https://doi.org/10.15560/17.2.637>.
- Cruz C.A.G., Caramaschi U., Fusinato, L.A., Brasileiro, C.A. 2019. Taxonomic review of *Dendrophryniscus brevipollicatus* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870, with revalidation of *D. imitator* (Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920) and *D. lauroi* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1926, and description of four new related species (Anura, Bufonidae). *Zootaxa* 4648:27–62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4648.1.2>.
- de Sá R.O., Tonini J.F.R., Huss H. van, Long A., Cuddy T., Forlani M.C., P... Haddad C.F.B. 2019a. Multiple connections between Amazonia and Atlantic Forest shaped phylogenetic and morphological diversity in the genus *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904 (Anura: Microhylidae: Gastrophryne). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 130:198–210. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2018.10.021>.
- de Sá R.O., Tonini J.F.R., Huss H. van, Long A., Cuddy T., Forlani M.C., ... Haddad C.F.B. 2019b. Corrigendum to: ‘Multiple connections between Amazonia and Atlantic Forest shaped the phylogenetic and morphological diversity of *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1904 (Anura: Microhylidae: Gastrophryninae)’. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 132:321. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2019.01.016>.

de Sá R.O., Tonini J.F.R., Huss H. van, Zaher H., Haddad C.F.B. 2019c. The unique traits of the subgenus *Unicus* within *Chiasmocleis* Méhely, 1094 [sic] (Anura, Microhylidae). *Zootaxa* 4646:585-590. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4646.3.8>.

Dias I.R., Novaes-e-Fagundes G., Neto A.M., Zina J., Garcia C., Recoder R.S., ... Solé M. 2020. A new large canopy-dwelling species of *Phyllodytes* Wagler, 1930 (Anura, Hylidae) from the Atlantic Forest of the state of Bahia, Northeastern Brazil. *PeerJ* 8:e8642. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/10.7717/peerj.8642>.

Dubois A. 1992. Notes sur la classification des Ranidae (Amphibiens anoures). *Bulletin Mensuel de la Société Linnéenne de Lyon* 61:305-352.

Dubois A., Ohler, A. & Pyron, A. 2021. New concepts and methods for phylogenetic taxonomy and nomenclature in zoology, exemplified by a new ranked cladonomy of recent amphibians (Lissamphibia). *Megataxa* 5:1-738. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/megataxa.5.1.1>.

Duellman W.E. 2015. Marsupial Frogs. Gastrotheca & Allied Genera. Johns Hopkins University Press, Baltimore.

Duellman W.E., Marion, A.B., Hedges, S.B. 2016. Phylogenetics, classification, and biogeography of the treefrogs (Amphibia: Anura: Arboranae). *Zootaxa* 4104:1-109. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4104.1.1>

Duellman W.E., Cannatella D.C. 2018. A new subgeneric name for a hemiphractid frog name that is preoccupied by a generic name of a fossil sponge. *Alytes* 36:194-199.

Duméril A.M., Bibron G. 1841. *Erpétologie générale, ou histoire naturelle des Reptiles*. Tome huitième, comprenant l'histoire générale des batraciens, et la description des cinquante-deux genres et des cent soixante-trois espèces des deux premiers sous-ordres: les péromèles qui n'ont pas de membres, et les anoures qui sont privées de la queue. Paris: Librairie Encyclopédique de Roret.

Faivovich J. 2002. A cladistic analysis of *Scinax* (Anura: Hylidae). *Cladistics* 18:367-393. doi: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0748-3007\(02\)00001-4](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0748-3007(02)00001-4).

Faivovich J., Haddad C.F.B., Garcia P.C.A., Frost D.R., Campbell J.A., Wheeler, W.C. 2005. Systematic review of the frog family Hylidae, with special reference to the Hylinae: phylogenetic analysis and taxonomic revision. *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 294:1-240. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1206/0003-0090\(2005\)294\[0001:srotff\]2.0.co;2](http://dx.doi.org/10.1206/0003-0090(2005)294[0001:srotff]2.0.co;2).

Faivovich J., Pereyra M.O., Luna M.C., Hertz A., Blotto B.L., Vásquez-Almazán C.R., ... Haddad C.F.B. 2018. On the monophyly and relationships of several genera of Hylini (Anura: Hylidae: Hylinae), with comments on recent taxonomic changes in Hylids. *South American Journal of Herpetology* 13:1–32. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2994/SAJH-D-17-00115.1>.

Faivovich J., Pinheiro P.D.P., Lyra M.L., Pereyra M.O., Baldo D., Muñoz A., ... Haddad C.F.B. 2021. Phylogenetic relationships of the *Boana pulchella* Group (Anura: Hylidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 155:106981. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2020.106981>.

Ferrão M., Lima A.P., Ron S, Santos S.P., Hanken, J. 2020. New species of leaf-litter toad of the *Rhinella margaritifera* species group (Anura: Bufonidae) from Amazonia. *Copeia* 108:967–986. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1643/CH2020043>.

Ferrão M., Moravec J., Hanken J., Lima, A.P. 2020. A new species of *Dendropsophus* (Anura, Hylidae) from southwestern Amazonia with a green bilobate vocal sac. *ZooKeys* 942:77–104. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3897/zookeys.942.51864>.

Ferreira R.B., Monico A.T., Cruz C.A.G., Guidorizzi C.E., Zocca C.Z., Canedo C., ... Pertel W. 2019. Anfíbios ameaçados de extinção no estado do Espírito Santo. Pp. 256–269 in Fraga C.N., Formigoni M.H. & Chaves F.G. (Org.). Fauna e flora ameaçadas de extinção no estado do Espírito Santo. Instituto Nacional da Mata Atlântica, Espírito Santo.

Fitzinger L.I. 1826. Neue classification der Reptilien nach ihren natürlichen Verwandtschaften nebst einer Verwandtschafts-Tafel und einem Verzeichnisse der Reptilien-Sammlung des K.K. zoologischen Museums zu Wien. J. G. Heubner. doi: <http://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.4683>.

Forti L.R., Haddad C.F.B., Leite F., Drummond L.O., Assis C.L., Crivellari L.B., ... Toledo L.F. 2019. Notes on vocalizations of Brazilian amphibians IV: advertisement calls of 20 Atlantic Forest frog species. *PeerJ* 7:e7612. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.7612>.

França D.P.F., Freitas M.A, Bernarde P.S., Peloso P.L.V.. 2013. New record of the humming frog *Chiasmocleis superciliaris* Morales and McDiarmid, 2009 (Amphibia: Microhylidae) in Brazil, the first outside its type locality. *Check List* 9:92–93. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15560/9.1.92>.

Frost D.R. 2021. Amphibian Species of the World: an Online Reference. Version 6.1 (March 10, 2021). Electronic Database accessible at DOI: <https://amphibiansoftheworld.amnh.org/index.php>. American Museum of Natural History, New York, USA. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5531/db.vz.0001>.

Gazoni T., Lyra M.L., Ron S.R., Strüssmann C., Baldo D., Narimatsu H., Pansonato A., ... Carvalho T.R. 2021. Revisiting the systematics of the *Leptodactylus melanonotus* group (Anura: Leptodactylidae): Redescription of *L. petersii* and revalidation of its junior synonyms. *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 290:117–134. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2020.12.002>.

Gravenhorst J.L.C. 1825. *Stombus*, eine neue Amphibien Gattung. *Isis von Oken* 1825: 920–922.

Heyer W.R. 1983. Variation and systematics of frogs of the genus *Cycloramphus* (Amphibia, Leptodactylidae). *Arquivos de Zoologia* 30:235–339. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3895.1.2>.

Izecksohn E. 1983. Uma nova espécie de *Zachaenus* Cope, do Estado do Espírito Santo, Brasil (Amphibia: Anura: Leptodactylidae). *Arquivos da Universidade Federal Rural do Rio de Janeiro* 5:7–11.

Jorge R.F., Ferrão M., Lima A.P. 2020. Out of bound: A new threatened Harlequin Toad (Bufonidae, *Atelopus*) from the outer borders of the Guiana Shield in central amazonia described through integrative taxonomy. *Diversity* 12:310. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/d12080310>.

Jowers M.J., Othman S.N., Borzée A., Rivas G.A., Sánchez-Ramírez S., Auguste R.J., ... Murphy J.C. 2021. Unraveling unique island colonization events in *Elachistocleis* frogs: phylogeography, cryptic divergence, and taxonomical implications. *Organisms Diversity & Evolution* 21:189–206. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1007/s13127-021-00487-y>.

Kaefer Í.L., Rojas-Zamora R.R., Ferrão M., Farias I.P., Lima A.P. 2019. A new species of *Amazophrynella* (Anura: Bufonidae) with two distinct advertisement calls. *Zootaxa* 4577: 316–334. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4577.2.5>.

Leal F., Leite F.S.F., Costa W.P., Nascimento L.B., Lourenço L.B., Garcia P.C.A. 2020. Amphibians from Serra do Cipó, Minas Gerais, Brasil. VI: A New Species of the *Physalaemus deimaticus* Group (Anura, Leptodactylidae). *Zootaxa* 4766:306–330. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.0000.0.0>.

Lima A.P., Ferrão M., Silva D.L. 2020. Not as widespread as thought: Integrative taxonomy reveals cryptic diversity in the Amazonian nurse frog *Allobates tinae* Melo-Sampaio, Oliveira and Prates, 2018 and description of a new species. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research* 58:1173–1194. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzs.12406>.

Lourenço A.C.C., Zina J., Catroli G.F., Kasahara S., Faivovich J., Haddad, C.F.B. 2016. A new species of the *Scinax catharinae* group (Anura: Hylidae) from southeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa* 4154:415–435. doi: <http://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4154.4.3>.

Lourenço A.C.C., Lingnau R., Haddad C.F.B., Faivovich J. 2019. A new species of the *Scinax catharinae* group (Anura: Hylidae) from the Highlands of Santa Catarina, Brazil. *South American Journal of Herpetology* 14:163–176. doi: <http://doi.org/10.2994/SAJH-D-18-00001.1>.

Lourenço A.C.C., Lacerda J.V, Cruz C.A.G., Nascimento L.B., Pombal Jr. J.P. 2020. A new species of the *Scinax catharinae* group (Anura: Hylidae) from the Atlantic rainforest of Northeastern Minas Gerais, Southeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa* 4878:305–321. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4878.2.5>.

Lourenço L.B., Targueta C.P., Baldo D., Nascimento J., Garcia P.C.A., Andrade G., ... Recco-Pimentel S.M. 2015. Phylogeny of frogs from the genus *Physalaemus* (Anura, Leptodactylidae) inferred from mitochondrial and nuclear gene sequences. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 92:204–216. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2015.06.011>.

Lyra M.L., Lourenço A.C.C., Pinheiro P.D.P., Pezzuti T.L., Baêta D., Barlow A., ... Faivovich J. 2020. High-throughput DNA sequencing of museum specimens sheds light on the long-missing species of the *Bokermannohyla claresignata* group (Anura: Hylidae: Cophomantini). *Zoological Journal of the Linnean Society*, 190:1235–1255. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1093/zoolinnean/zlaa033>.

Maciel A.O., Hoogmoed M.S. 2011. Taxonomy and distribution of caecilian amphibians (Gymnophiona) of Brazilian Amazonia, with a key to their identification. *Zootaxa* 2984:1–53. doi: <http://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2984.1.1>.

Maciel A.O., Castro T.M., Sturaro M.J., Silva I.E.C., Ferreira J.G., dos Santos R., ... Schneider I. 2019. Phylogenetic systematics of the Neotropical caecilian amphibian *Luetkenotyphlus* (Gymnophiona: Siphonopidae) including the description of a new species from the vulnerable Brazilian Atlantic Forest. *Zoologischer Anzeiger* 281:76–83. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcz.2019.07.001>.

Magalhães F.M., Lyra M.L., Carvalho T.R., Baldo D., Brusquetti F., Burella P., ... Garda A.A. 2020a. Taxonomic review of South American Butter Frogs: Phylogeny, geographic patterns, and species delimitation in the *Leptodactylus latrans* species group (Anura: Leptodactylidae). *Herpetological Monographs* 34:131–177. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1655/HERPMONOGRAPHS-D-19-00012>.

Magalhães F.M., Brandão R.A., Garda A.A., Mângia S. 2020b. Revisiting the generic position and acoustic diagnosis of *Odontophrynus salvatori* (Anura: Odontophrynidae). *Herpetological Journal* 30:189–196. doi: <https://doi.org/10.33256/hj30.4.189196>.

Mângia S., Koroiva R., Santana D.J. 2020a. A new tiny toad species of *Amazophrynella* (Anura: Bufonidae) from east of the Guiana Shield in Amazonia, Brazil. *PeerJ* 8:e9887. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9887>.

Mângia S., Oliveira E.F., Santana D.J., Koroiva R., Paiva F., Garda A.A. 2020b. Revising the taxonomy of *Proceratophrys* Miranda-Ribeiro, 1920 (Anura: Odontophrynidae) from the Brazilian semiarid Caatinga: Morphology, calls and molecules support a single widespread species. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research* 58: 1151–1172. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jzs.12365>.

Marques R.B., Haddad C.F.B., Garda A.A. 2021. There and back again from monotypy: A new species of the casque-headed *Corythomantis* Boulenger 1896 (Anura, Hylidae) from the Espinhaço mountain range, Brazil. *Herpetologica* 77(1):56-71. doi:<http://doi.org/10.1655/0018-0831-77.1.56>.

Melo-Sampaio P.R., Souza M.B. 2015. New and noteworthy distributional records of treefrogs (Anura) from southwestern Amazonia. *Check List* 11:1681. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15560/11.4.1681>.

Melo-Sampaio P.R., Prates I., Peloso P.L.V., Recoder R., Dal Vechio F., Marques-Souza S., Rodrigues, M.T. 2020. A new nurse frog from Southwestern Amazonian highlands, with notes on the phylogenetic affinities of *Allobates alessandroi* (Aromobatidae). *Journal of Natural History* 54:43–62. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2020.1727972>.

Merrem B. 1820. Versuch eines Systems der Amphibien [Tentamen systematis amphibiorum]. Marburg: Johann Christian Krieger. <http://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.5037>.

Moraes L.J.C.L., Pavan D., Lima A.P. 2019. A new nurse frog of *Allobates masniger-nidicola* complex (Anura, Aromobatidae) from the east bank of Tapajós River, eastern Amazonia. *Zootaxa* 4648:401–434.

Novaes-e-Fagundes G., Araujo-Vieira K., Entiauspe-Neto O.M., Roberto I.J., Orrico V.G.D., Solé M., Haddad C.F.B., Loebmann D. 2021. A new species of *Scinax* Wagler (Hylidae: Scinaxini) from the tropical forests of Northeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa* 4903:1–41. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4903.1.1>.

Oliveira E.A., Silva L.A., Silva E.A.P., Guimarães K.L.A., Penhacek M., Martínez J.G., ... Hernández-Ruz E.J. 2020. Four new species of *Pristimantis* Jiménez de la Espada, 1870 (Anura: Craugastoridae) in the eastern Amazon. PLoS ONE 15:e0229971. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229971>.

Ortega-Andrade H.M., Venegas P.J. 2014. A new synonym for *Pristimantis luscombei* (Duellman and Mendelson 1995) and the description of a new species of *Pristimantis* from the upper Amazon basin (Amphibia: Craugastoridae). *Zootaxa* 3895:31–57.

Pansonato A., Motta A., Cacciali P., Haddad C.F.B., Strüssmann C., Jansen M. 2020. On the identity of species of *Oreobates* (Anura: Craugastoridae) from Central South America, with the description of a new species from Bolivia. *Journal of Herpetology* 54:393–412. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1670/20-001>.

Pereira A.J.G., Carvalho, V.T., Almeida, A.P., Rojas, R.R., Gordo, M., Frazão, L. ... Menin, M. 2021. New records of the Horned toad (*Rhinella ceratophrys*): filling distribution gaps in lowland forests in the Brazilian Amazon. *Herpetological Notes* 14:435–438.

Pereyra M.O., Blotto B.L., Baldo D., Chaparro J.C., Ron S.R., Elias-Costa A.J., Iglesias P.P., Venegas P.J., Thomé M.T.C., Ospina-Sarria J.J., Maciel N.M., Rada M., Kolenc F., Borteiro C., Rivera-Correa M., Rojas-Runjaic F.C.M., Moravec J., De La Riva I., Wheeler W.C., Castroviejo-Fisher S., Grant T., Haddad C.F.B., Faivovich J. 2021. Evolution in the genus *Rhinella*: A total evidence phylogenetic analysis of Neotropical true toads (Anura: Bufonidae). *Bulletin of the American Museum of Natural History* 447(1):1-156.

Pinheiro P., Pezzuti T.L., Berneck B.V.M., Lyra M.L., Lima R.C.L., Leite F.S.F. 2021. A new cryptic species of the genus *Aplastodiscus* (Anura: Hylidae) similar to *A. cavicola*. *Salamandra* 57:27–43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4541651>.

Pyron R.A., Wiens J.J. 2011. A large-scale phylogeny of Amphibia including over 2800 species, and a revised classification of extant frogs, salamanders, and caecilians. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 61:543-583. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2011.06.012>.

de Sá F.P., Haddad C.F.B., Gray M.M., Verdade V.K., Thomé M.T.C., Rodrigues M.T., Zamudio K.R. 2020. Male-male competition and repeated evolution of terrestrial breeding in Atlantic Coastal Forest frogs *Evolution* 74: 459–475. <https://doi.org/10.1111/evo.13879>.

Sabbag A.F., Lyra M.L., Zamudio K.R., Haddad C.F.B., Feio R.N., Leite F.S.F., Gasparini J.L., Brasileiro C.A. 2018. Molecular phylogeny of Neotropical rock frogs reveals a long history of vicariant diversification in the Atlantic forest. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 122: 142–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ympev.2018.01.017>.

Santos M.T.T., Oliveira S.H., Carvalho T.R., Zaidan B.F., Silva N.R., Berneck B.V.M., Garcia P.C.A. 2019. A new species of *Paratelmatobius* (Anura: Leptodactylidae: Paratelmatobiinae) from the Atlantic Forest of southern Brazil. *Zootaxa* 4648:473–493. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4648.3.4>.

Santos-Pereira M., Pombal Jr. J.P., Rocha C.F.D. 2018. Anuran amphibians in state of Paraná, southern Brazil. *Biota Neotropica* 18:e20170322. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/1676-0611-BN-2017-0322>.

Segalla M.V., Caramaschi U., Cruz C.A.G., Garcia P.C.A., Grant T., Haddad C.F.B., ... Langone J. A. 2019. Brazilian amphibians: list of species. *Herpetologia Brasileira* 8:65–96.

Silva L.A., Magalhães F.M., Thomassen H., Leite F.S.F., Garda A.A., Brandão R.A., ... Carvalho, T.R. 2020. Unraveling the species diversity and relationships in the *Leptodactylus mystaceus* complex (Anura: Leptodactylidae), with the description of three new Brazilian species. *Zootaxa* 4779:151–189. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4779.2.1>.

Souza J.R.D., Ferrão M., Hanken J., Lima A.P. 2020. A new nurse frog (Anura: *Allobates*) from Brazilian Amazonia with a remarkably fast multi-noted advertisement call. *PeerJ* 8:e9979. doi: <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9979>.

Steindachner, F. 1863. Über einige neue Batrachier aus den Sammlungen des Wiener Museums. *Sitzungsberichte der Kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften, Mathematisch-Naturwissenschaftliche Classe* 48:186–192.

Sturaro M.J., Costa J.C.L., Maciel A.O., Lima-Filho G.R., Rojas-Runjaic F.J.M., Mejia D.P., ... Peloso P.L.V. 2020. Resolving the taxonomic puzzle of *Boana cinerascens* (Spix, 1824), with resurrection of *Hyla granosa gracilis* Melin, 1941 (Anura: Hylidae). *Zootaxa* 4750:1–30. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4750.1.1>.

Taucce P.P.G., Zaidan B.F., Zaher H., Garcia P.C.A. 2019. A new species of *Ischnocnema* Reinhardt and Lütken, 1862 (Anura: Brachycephalidae) of the *I. lactea* species series from southeastern Brazil. *Zootaxa* 4706:531–545. doi: <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.4706.4.3>.

Tauce P.P.G., Costa-Campos C.E., Haddad C.F.B., Carvalho T.R. 2020. A new Amazonian species of the diminutive frog genus *Adelophryne* (Anura: Brachycephaloidea: Eleutherodactylidae) from the State of Amapá, northern Brazil. *Copeia* 108:746–757. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1643/CH-19-254>.

Tauce P.P.G., Nascimento J.S., Trevisan C.C., Leite F.S.F., Santana D.J., Haddad C.F.B., Napoli M.F. 2020. A new rupicolous species of the *Pristimantis conspicillatus* group (Anura: Brachycephaloidea: Craugastoridae) from Central Bahia, Brazil. *Journal of Herpetology* 54:245–257. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1670/19-114>.

Tschudi J. J. von. 1838. Classification der Batrachier mit Berücksichtigung der fossilen Thiere dieser Abtheilung der Reptilien. Neuchâtel: Petitpierre.

Vittorazi S.E., Lourenço L.B., Zattera M.L., Weber L.N., Recco-Pimentel S.M., Bruschi D.P. 2021. Cytogenetic and genetic data support *Crossodactylus aeneus* Müller, 1924 as a new synonym of *C. gaudichaudii* Duméril & Bibron, 1841 (Amphibia, Anura) *Genetics and Molecular Biology* 44:e20200301. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-4685-gmb-2020-0301>.

Wagler J. 1830. Natürliches System der Amphibien, mit vorangehender Classification der Säugthiere und Vogel. Ein Beitrag zur vergleichenden Zoologie. München, Stuttgart and Tübingen: J. G. Cotta. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.58730>.

Zornosa-Torres C., Augusto-Alves G., Lyra M.L., Silva Jr J.C., Garcia P.C.A., Leite F., ..., Toledo L.F. 2020. Anurans of the Caparaó National Park and surroundings, southeast Brazil. *Biota Neotropica* 20:e20190882. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1676-0611-bn-2019-0882>.